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3 **The Flora and Fauna of NEOM, Tabuk Province, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia**

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36 **Abstract:** Species lists as of 2024 for terrestrial and marine mammals, birds, fishes, herpetofauna,
37 and higher plants were compiled for the NEOM giga-project region in Tabuk Province of the
38 Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. For documented native species, there are 56 mammals, 310 bird species,
39 476 marine fish species, 59 herpetofauna species, no native freshwater fish species, and 590
40 vascular plant species. These lists are based on published technical literature and intensive
41 biodiversity surveys conducted since 2018. This inventory of species represents one of the most
42 comprehensive for any area in the Arabian Peninsula. Terrestrial, freshwater, and marine
43 invertebrates remain as major gaps in NEOM's inventory of its biota.

44
45 تم جرد وتوثيق الأنواع المحلية للتدييات البرية والبحرية والطيور والأسماك والزواحف والنباتات في ارجاء مشروع نيوم في منطقة تبوك
46 نوغاً 310 نوغاً من التدييات البرية والبحرية، و56 بالمملكة العربية السعودية في عام ٢٠٢٤م. بالنسبة للأنواع المحلية الموثقة، هناك
47 نوغاً من الزواحف، ولم يوثق أي أنواع من أسماك المياه العذبة، كما تم توثيق 59 من الطيور، و476 نوغاً من الأسماك البحرية، و
48 نوغاً من النباتات العليا. بالنسبة لبعض الأصناف، هناك بعض الأنواع التي تمت ملاحظتها ولكن لم يتم تحديدها بعد، ومن المتوقع 590
49 وجود بعض الأنواع المحتملة ولكن لم يتم توثيقها بعد. تعتمد هذه القوائم على الأدبيات المنشورة والمسوحات المكثفة للتنوع البيولوجي في
50 المنطقة والتي تم إجراؤها منذ عام 2018. ويمثل هذا الجرد للأنواع المحلية من الحيوانات والنباتات واحداً من أكثر قوائم الجرد شمولاً
51 لأي منطقة في شبه الجزيرة العربية. ولا تزال اللافقاريات الأرضية، والمياه العذبة، والبحرية تمثل فجوات كبيرة في مخزون نيوم من
52 الكائنات الحية.

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54 **Keywords:** Arabian; biodiversity; flora; fauna; inventory; Red Sea; Tabuk; Kingdom of Saudi
55 Arabia; NEOM

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Introduction

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's (KSA) NEOM 'giga-project' is in the northwest corner of the country in Tabuk Province bounded by the northeastern Red Sea and Gulf of Aqaba (NEOM, 2024; Fig. 1). An important goal of the NEOM project is to minimize impacts of development on nature, including biodiversity. Knowledge of the species that occur in NEOM was incomplete when development was initiated in 2018 so understanding potential impacts was challenging. To help fill this gap in knowledge of species, the biodiversity of this region has been intensively surveyed since 2018 as part of NEOM's sustainable development program and NEOM Nature Reserve's protected area activation. These recent biodiversity surveys have targeted a wide range of taxa and covered multiple locations, habitats, and ecosystems, making this one of the most intensively surveyed biotas in the region.

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Figure 1. Major Ecosystem Types of NEOM: (1) Northern Red Sea & Gulf of Aqaba; (2) Coastal Lowlands; (3) Madyan Range; (4) Hisma Desert; (5) Tabuk Sandstone; and (6) Harrat lava fields.

NEOM’s location at a crossroads of major biogeographic units—Saharan (Palearctic), Arabian (Palearctic & Afrotropical), Mediterranean (Palearctic), Irano-Turanian (Palearctic), for example (Vincent, 2008)—and two global migratory bird flyways (that is, the Black Sea/Mediterranean and West Asia/East Africa flyways (BirdLife International, 2024ab) contributes to a potentially rich and distinct assemblages of species. Growing evidence also suggests that NEOM’s reefs may have high rates of endemism of corals as well as unique groundwater-regulated reef and seagrass ecosystems. Corals here may also be among the world’s most adaptable to climate-change (Fine

83 et al., 2013; Berumen et al., 2019; Eladawy et al., 2022; Terraneo et al., 2023; Permanent
84 Delegation of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to UNESCO, 2024). Further, modelling indicates that
85 the far northwest of Saudi Arabia contains some of the highest conservation priority habitat in the
86 Kingdom (Boland and Burwell, 2022).

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88 Prior to the initiation of recent taxonomic and ecological surveys in NEOM in 2018, the technical
89 literature on the fauna and flora of northwest Saudi Arabia and the northern Red Sea was limited
90 to several regional and focused publications, including significant contributions for a range of taxa
91 (Box 1). Intensive biological surveys initiated in 2018 to support the development of NEOM have
92 verified many known species and added numerous additional species for a range of higher taxa.
93 These recent surveys have been distributed across NEOM's ecosystem types, habitats, and seasons.

95
96 **Box 1.** Significant contributions to the native species and ecology of the NEOM and Arabian Peninsula
97 region that were available prior to and during the intensive surveys initiated in 2018 include:

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99 Vesey-Fitzgerald (1957), Lewis et al. (1965), Harrison (1968), Zohary (1973), Aleem (1979), Nader (1979), Farag & Banaja (1980),
100 Büttiker & Harrison (1982), Hulings & Kirkman (1982), Ilani & Bouskila (1982), Nader (1982), Chaudary (1983), Krupp (1983),
101 Schulz & Whitney (1985), Green (1986), Takhtajan (1986), Arnold (1987), Colonette (1988, 1999), Gasperetti (1988), Ormond et
102 al. (1988), Al Nafie (1989), Delany (1989), Miller (1989), Nader (1989, 1990), Ady (1991), Al Safadi & Nader (1991), Harrison
103 & Bates (1991), Kingdon (1991), Miller & Nyber (1991), Nader (1991), Thouless et al. (1991), White & Leonard (1991), Sheppard
104 et al. (1992), Amr et al. (1994), KBAP (1994), El Ghani (1996), Miller & Cope (1996), Quemsiyeh et al. (1996), Seddon et al.
105 (1997), Ghazanfar & Fisher (1998), Martin & Hirschfield (1998), Chaudhary (1999-2001), Chaudhary & Al Jowaid (1999), (Danin
106 (1999), Borzatti von Lowenstern et al. (2000), Nader (2000), Disi et al. (2001), Mallon & Kingswood (2001), Watts & Al Nafie
107 (2003), Abu Baker et al. (2004), AbuZinada (2004), Qarqaz et al. (2004), El Alqamy & Baha El Din (2006), Judas et al. (2006),
108 Spalton & Al Hikami (2006), Al Johany (2007), Wilms and Böhme (2007), Benda et al. (2008), Boulos (2008), Cope (2008),
109 Cunningham & Wacher (2009), Al Abbasi et al. (2010), Alharbi (2010), Cunningham & Wronski (2010), Jennings (2010), Amr &
110 Disi (2011), Mallon & Budd (2011), Miller et al. (2011), Amr (2012), Carranza & Arnold (2012), Cox et al. (2012), Metallinou et
111 al. (2012), Seddon et al. (2013), Aloufi & Eid (2014, 2019), Bray et al. (2014), Shobrak & Aloufi (2014), Aloufi & Amr (2015),
112 García et al. (2015), Mancini et al. (2015), Metallinou et al. (2015), Moawed & Ansari (2015), Symes et al. (2015), Abramov et al.
113 (2016), Almutairi et al. (2016), Aloufi et al. (2016), El Shaffai (2016), Moawed (2016), Stuart & Stuart (2016), Islam & Boug
114 (2017), Aloufi & Amr (2018), Amr et al. (2018), Basahi (2018), Golani & Fricke (2018), Paray & Al Sadoon (2018), Surur &
115 Thomas (2018), Aloufi & Eid (2019), Aloufi et al. (2019), Costa et al. (2019), Fakhry & El-Kenany (2019), Ghazanfar et al. (2019),
116 Qurban et al. (2019), Terraneo (2019), Al Shehri et al. (2020), Boland & Alsuhaibany (2020), Eid et al. (2020), Freyhof et al.
117 (2020), Islam et al. (2020), Eid & Mallon (2021), Islam et al. (2021), Shimada et al. (2021), Šmid et al. (2021), Ansari et al. (2022),
118 Egan (2022), Garzon et al. (2022), Al Atawi et al. (2023), Al Bakre (2023), Al Obaid et al. (2023), BirdLife International (2023),
119 Forrest & Neale (2023), Mallon et al. (2023), Mensoor (2023), Al Ahmari et al. (2024), Al Bakre et al. (2024), Al Obaid et al.
120 (2023), BirdLife International (2023), Egan et al. (2023), Forrest & Neale (2023), Mallon et al. (2023), Mensoor (2023), Al Ahmari
121 et al. (2024), Alatawi (2024), Al Malki et al. (2024), Dunford et al. (2024), Faure et al. (2024), Licata et al. (2024), Pola et al.
122 (2024), Thomas (2024), Haggon et al. (2025), Alzahrani et al. 2026

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125 Here we present updated lists of selected taxa as of December 2024, informed by intensive surveys
126 since 2018 in NEOM. Our aim is to provide species data that supports biodiversity research and
127 conservation and environmental assessments and initiatives (for example, Saudi Green Initiative,
128 Convention on Biological Diversity, Sustainable Development Goals, Red Sea Sustainability
129 Initiative, PERSGA and Jeddah Convention, Convention on the Conservation of Wildlife and
130 Their Natural Habitats in Countries of the Gulf Cooperation Council, and RAMSAR Convention).
131 Species data can inform the evaluations of the Kingdom's UNESCO World Heritage nominations
132 for the Red Sea and Gulf of Aqaba (Permanent Delegation of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to
133 UNESCO, 2024) and bioclimatic refugia of western Arabia (Permanent Delegation of the
134 Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to UNESCO, 2023). Species lists can inform future research on whether

135 NEOM's biodiversity constitutes a 'hotspot' of species or higher taxonomic diversity or simply
136 appears to have an elevated richness because it is exceptionally well surveyed. Evaluation of the
137 biogeographic affinities of different taxa can help determine the distinctiveness, if any, of the
138 taxonomic assemblage of this regional crossroad. We identify taxonomic and habitat-associated
139 gaps in knowledge and recommend further survey efforts to address these.

140

141 **Materials and Methods**

142

143 *Study Area*

144

145 *Ecoregions & Ecosystem Types*

146 NEOM covers approximately 26,555 km² of land and sea in the northwest of the Kingdom of Saudi
147 Arabia (Fig. 1). It includes portions of three terrestrial ecoregions: Arabian desert shrublands;
148 Eastern Mediterranean conifer-broadleaf forests and woodlands/shrublands; and North Arabian
149 desert (Dinerstein et al., 2017), as well as portions of the Southwestern Arabian Coast freshwater
150 ecoregion (Abell et al., 2008) and Northern and Central Red Sea marine ecoregion (Spalding et
151 al., 2007).

152

153 NEOM harbors eleven of the 65 terrestrial and freshwater ecosystem types and marine ecosystem
154 types clusters identified in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's (KSA) revised protected area system
155 plan (NCW, 2024): Gulf of Al 'Aqabah Cluster; Northern Red Sea Cluster; Red Sea Mangroves;
156 Northern Red Sea Shoreline; North Tihamah Coastal Plain; Madyan Hills and Mountains; Madyan,
157 Hisma, and Harrat ar-Raha Mountain Summits; Hisma Plateau; Northern Sandstone Plain and
158 Plateaus; Northwestern Harrahs; and Hijaz and Madyan Montane Wadis. Here, we use an adapted,
159 simplified version of these eleven ecosystem types to map six major ecosystem types (Fig. 1).
160 These six major ecosystem types are: (1) Northern Red Sea and Gulf of Aqaba marine, which
161 extends from nearshore reefs and seagrass meadows to abyssal brine pools; (2) Coastal Lowlands
162 (comprised of drift deposits of wadi and aeolian sands, gravel sheets, granitic sand bowls, raised
163 reef limestone, sandstone outcrops, and limestone-based deposits); (3) Madyan Range granitic and
164 volcanic mountains reaching to 2,580 m; (4) Hisma Desert, a distinct zone of outcropping
165 sandstone and drift deposits comprising wadi alluvium and aeolian sand that extends northward to
166 Wadi Rum in Jordan and southwards to Wadi al-Disah in the Prince Mohammed bin Salman Royal
167 Reserve; (5) the Tabuk Sandstone tablelands; and (6) Harrat (*harrah*) lava plateaus (basalt cobbles
168 overlying sandstone) [2, 146, 147] (Fig. 1). Substrates are largely unaltered parent rock. Only at
169 the highest elevations (above *ca.* 1,800 m) has there been obvious creation of organic soil layers.

170

171 *Physiographic Regions*

172 NEOM's physiographic regions include the following (in accordance with Vincent [2008]):

173

174 *Marine*

175 NEOM encompasses approximately 3,724 km² of the Gulf of Aqaba and northern Red Sea. The
176 eastern coast of the Gulf of Aqaba supports narrow fringing reefs and seagrass meadows, in places.
177 Both quickly fall away to depths reaching 1,850 m within a few kilometers from the coast. The
178 marine ecosystems from Ras Alsheik Hamid to Sharma are complex with broad seagrass meadows,
179 fringing reefs, coral bommies, uplifted limestone islands, and enclosed bays. Here abundant
180 groundwater infusions modify marine ecosystems and strong prevailing northerly winds help

181 isolate marine communities. Further south along the coast the marine ecosystems are northerly
182 extensions of the fringing and offshore reefs characteristic of much of the eastern Red Sea coast.
183

184 *Coastal and near-coastal plains*

185 The coastal and near-coastal plain constitute the northern-most section of the Tihamah Plain, a
186 near-coastal plain with lowlands that runs more or less the entire length of the western coast of
187 Arabia. South of Jeddah it widens to a maximum of 40 km. It is much narrower and discontinuous
188 in NEOM (approximately 4,648 km² in NEOM), and this is especially true along the Gulf of
189 Aqaba. Most of the plains are covered by Quaternary and Tertiary gravel and cobble deposits.
190

191 *Red Sea Escarpment*

192 The Madyan Mountains of the Red Sea Escarpment, in the northwest of the Kingdom occupy a
193 substantial part of the NEOM area (approximately 9,022 km²). The Quaternary and Tertiary gravel
194 deposits characteristic of the near-coastal zone ends abruptly and mountains of the Arabian Shield
195 (i.e. composed of ancient, Precambrian rock) predominate. More conspicuous vegetation growth
196 (i.e. with relatively dense tree and / or dwarf shrub cover) is associated with the larger wadis at
197 lower to medium elevations, but above 1,500 m, the gentle slopes can also support species rich
198 dwarf shrub / perennial herb communities, with scattered trees a conspicuous feature at the highest
199 elevations.
200

201 *Hisma*

202 The Hisma Desert is a high-elevation sandstone plateau with spectacular Permo-Triassic sandstone
203 buttes and mesas that are scattered across the plain, rising from red sands. Such rocky exposures
204 are typical inselberg habitats that, in some cases, can constitute important refuges for both flora
205 and fauna. The original sandstone landscape is, therefore, a highly eroded plateau, and this has
206 given rise to numerous canyons. In some areas, the sandstone rock has been weathered to ground-
207 level, giving rise to a characteristic sandstone pavement landscape (Brown & Ayasrah, 2023). This
208 covers an area of about 6,487 km² in NEOM alone and constitutes a southerly extension of the
209 desert ecosystem of the Wadi Rum World Heritage Site in Jordan.
210

211 *Harrat Ar Raha*

212 Tertiary and Quaternary basaltic lava fields of north-western Saudi Arabia cover extensive sections
213 of the Arabian Plate. In NEOM, Harrat Ar Raha encroaches on the southeastern-most section,
214 occupying a quite sizeable area of about 1,074 km² in NEOM alone.
215

216 *Tabuk-Sirhan-Turayf Plain*

217 Along the eastern edge of NEOM the Tabuk sandstones abut the Hisma sandstones and lie
218 underneath the flood basalt lavas of the harrat. They cover roughly 1,536 km² of NEOM. Sandstone
219 rock pavements—a globally rare ecosystem type found here and in the Hisma desert (Sayre et al.
220 2014, Brown & Ayasrah 2023)—are interspersed with rocky outcrops and dunes, as well as broad
221 sand, gravel, and boulder-filled wadis (Al Nafie, 1989; Watts & Al Nafie, 2003).
222

223 *Habitat Types*

224 NEOM has identified 103 major terrestrial habitat types and 42 major terrestrial vegetation types
225 (Buro Happold & Brown, 2022). Land habitats are diverse, ranging from inland sabkha, gravel
226 plains, and large sand dunes and sheets to rugged granitic peaks, permanent montane seeps, lava

227 plateaus (*harrah*), and reedbeds (Buro Happold & Brown, 2022). Changes in ecosystems over
228 distance can be dramatic such that, at times, one can travel from winter snowclad peaks to coral
229 reefs in roughly 40 km (for example, Jibal Al Lawz range to Gulf of Aqaba). Munro and others
230 (2022) identified 25 marine and associated coastal habitat types in NEOM. Gulko and others
231 (2024) have refined earlier classifications and developed a system of 23 reef types for NEOM's
232 waters.

233
234 Based on the results of Buro Happold and Brown (2022) and other studies, dwarf shrubland is the
235 most widespread terrestrial habitat type. Below about 1,200 m, *Haloxylon salicornicum* is the most
236 common community with species such as *Artemisia sieberi* and *Tanacetum sinaicum* becoming
237 more prevalent at higher elevations. Other common shrubs and dwarf shrubs include *Retama*
238 *raetam* and *Zygophyllum molle*. Scattered trees and open woodland occur at all elevations. In the
239 lowlands the dominant species is *Vachellia tortillis* ssp. *tortilis* scattered in plains and foothills or
240 concentrated in wadis or alluvial fans. *Vachellia gerrardi* woodland is typical of higher elevations.
241 Scattered trees occur at higher elevations, including rare and relict species, such as *Prunus*
242 *korshinskyi*, *Pistacia khinjuk*, *Salix acmophylla*, *Ficus palmata* ssp. *palmata*, and *Juniperus*
243 *turbinata*. The flora of the higher elevations (generally greater than 1,700 m) is remarkable for
244 assemblages of species that favor cooler and wetter conditions, with high peaks effectively
245 functioning as climatic refugia for numerous species. Coastal vegetation is dominated by
246 halophytic dwarf scrub, such as *Zygophyllum album*, *Limonium axillare*, and *Suaeda vermiculata*.
247 *Tamarix nilotica*, *Halocnemum strobilaceum*, *Juncus rigidus*, and *Aeluropus lagopoides* also
248 occur.

249
250 Twenty-one marine habitats and four marine-associated coastal habitats have been identified,
251 including seagrass meadows, coral reefs, seamounts, abyssal deeps, abyssal brine pools,
252 mangroves, lagoons, and reef flats (Munro et al., 2022). Photic reefs fringe most of the coastline
253 and islands. Ras Alsheikh Hamid, the areas east of Alkhuraybah Bay and south towards Duba, as
254 well as shallow fringes of the Gulf of Aqaba support a range of coral reefs and patch reefs.
255 Substantial areas of mesophotic reef are present along the coastline of the Gulf of Aqaba, driven
256 by the near-vertical nature of the bathymetry. Seagrass meadows cover extensive areas. Coral-
257 topped seamounts occur offshore. Brine pools occur at the bottom of the Gulf of Aqaba.
258 Groundwater-regulated reefs extend from Ras Alsheikh Hamid to Alkhuraybah (NEOM) Bay,
259 potentially supporting some of the highest rates of species endemism of corals and, possibly, other
260 reef-associated invertebrates known. A system of 23 reef types for NEOM's waters has recently
261 been developed (Gulko et al., 2024).

262 *Climate*

263
264 The climate of NEOM varies considerably between four climatic zones (Vincent 2008) but is
265 generally characterized by low rainfall (0 to 4 mm/year) and high temperatures (~50 °C in the
266 summer) that are typical of hyper-arid, arid, and semi-arid environments, corresponding to extreme
267 desert to semi-desert, respectively (Shmida, 1985). The hot season is from June to September with
268 maximum temperatures in July and August. The cooler season is from October to May with
269 minimum temperatures in January. The coastal plains experience the highest temperatures,
270 reaching a maximum of ~50°C in the summer, as well as the lowest annual rainfall, as low as 0 to
271 4 mm in some areas. By contrast, the monthly average minimum and maximum temperatures of
272 the montane areas of NEOM (the Madyan Range) are no more than 15°C to 25°C. Sub-zero winter

273 temperatures are not uncommon on the highest peaks, such as on the Jibal al Lawz range with the
274 lowest recorded temperature in the past decade reaching -13.9°C (J. Ware, pers. comm. 2025).
275 Annual rainfall is highest in the mountain ranges and plateau areas to the east, ranging upwards to
276 ~109 mm. Localized rainfall events occur episodically everywhere in NEOM.

277

278 *Methods to Compile Species Lists*

279

280 We compiled species lists for higher taxa that have been recently surveyed within the boundary of
281 NEOM. To do this, we reviewed published literature and unpublished survey data, developed draft
282 species lists for each taxon which were then reviewed and revised, where needed, by taxonomic
283 specialists. The target taxa are mammals, birds, reptiles, amphibians, vascular plants, and marine
284 fishes. Species lists were not compiled for terrestrial, freshwater, or marine invertebrates, fungi,
285 bryophytes, lichen, algae, protozoans, bacteria, viruses, or other life forms. Invertebrates represent
286 a significant gap as they typically make up most species in any local or regional biota (May, 1988).
287 Native freshwater fish have not been adequately surveyed, though only one native species is
288 recorded to occur in the region (see Krupp, 1993; García et al., 2019; Freyhof et al., 2020).

289

290 A confirmed detection is defined as (1) an observation, collection, or detection (for example,
291 camera-trap image, video, specimen, carcass, eDNA detection, distinct scat [such as that of Indian
292 crested porcupine *Hystrix indica*] [footprints were not considered as adequate evidence]) recorded
293 in a published or unpublished survey (such as biodiversity baseline surveys conducted as part of
294 development related Environmental Impact Assessments) by a specialist(s) for the taxonomic
295 group, including field observation (not necessarily collection) or (2) inclusion of a documented
296 species locality within NEOM from a taxonomic or ecological peer-reviewed technical publication
297 or survey report (published or unpublished) by a taxonomic specialist or group (for example,
298 taxonomic specialists of consulting firms hired by NEOM). Methods for individual surveys
299 differed and were selected by specialists for their efficacy to gather data for their target taxon.
300 Survey methods employed by specialists are detailed in their respective reports (Appendix A). In
301 the case of vascular plants, the compiled list of species recorded during numerous surveys and by
302 numerous field researchers were scrutinized by specialists with knowledge of NEOM and the
303 wider region, to screen out likely misidentifications.

304

305 Taxonomic specialists were asked to contribute the following, where possible:

306

- 307 (1) an assessment of how many species they consider yet to be recorded;
- 308 (2) for some taxa, a list of species not yet confirmed but likely to occur within NEOM;
- 309 (3) any notable biogeographic or biodiversity features of their taxon within NEOM.

310

311 We define native species as those that occur naturally within NEOM. This includes native species
312 that are present during part of their lifecycle, such as migratory species. Species that are known or
313 assumed to be introduced by humans are not counted as native species, though commensal species
314 are counted. Species reintroduced through NEOM's rewilding initiative are counted as native
315 species, including counterpart subspecies, such as the red-legged ostrich (*Struthio camelus*
316 *camelus*) brought in as a functional ecological counterpart subspecies for the now extinct Arabian
317 ostrich (*Struthio camelus syriacus*), though these two subspecies may, in fact, be the same
318 (Robinson & Mathee, 1999; Miller et al., 2011). Vagrant birds are included in the native species

319 list. Larger domesticated and feral terrestrial mammals or birds are not counted as native wildlife
320 species. Commensal birds and rodents are included in the lists. Vertebrate species and family
321 follow IUCN (2024). Plant species and family names follow the World Checklist of Vascular
322 Plants (Govaerts et al., 2021).

323

324 **Results**

325

326 *Native Species*

327 The numbers of species for each target taxon confirmed to occur within NEOM are presented in
328 Table 1 and the native species lists are provided in Appendix B (Tables B1-B15).

329

330 **Table 1.** Total number of native species confirmed within NEOM as of December 2025.

331

332 Taxon	# native species confirmed in NEOM	# likely to occur, unconfirmed or 333 occurs but species identity unconfirmed
334 Vascular Plants	590	96
335 <i>Marine Plants</i>	11	not assessed
336 Reptiles	58	9
337 <i>Marine Reptiles</i>	2	3
338 Amphibians	1	1
339 Birds	310	23
340 Mammals	55	10
341 <i>Small Mammals</i>	13	1
342 <i>Bats</i>	17	9
343 <i>Marine Mammals</i>	10	4
344 Marine Fishes	476	not assessed

345

346 **Discussion**

347

348 We present a list for native species for multiple taxa that occur in NEOM based on previous
349 published literature and a large set of recent surveys since 2018 (Table 1, Tables B1-B15). The
350 total richness of each taxon cannot be estimated using rarefaction curves (Chao et al., 2014) as
351 there was no standardization among survey approaches and effort. However, some of the taxon
352 specialists who compiled the native species lists estimate the ‘completeness’ of the lists based on
353 their knowledge of the regional flora or fauna, uncertainties in taxonomy, and the survey efforts to
354 date across NEOM as follows: birds (greater than 95%), mammals (greater than 90%),
355 herpetofauna (greater than 75%), marine fishes (greater than 60%), and vascular plants (greater
356 than 70%).

357

358 *Terrestrial & Marine Mammals*

359

360 *Larger mammals*

361 Fifteen native larger terrestrial mammal species occur in NEOM (Appendix B). Three of these, the
362 Arabian gazelle (*Gazella arabica*), sand gazelle (*Gazella marica*), and Arabian oryx (*Oryx*
363 *leucoryx*), have been reintroduced since 2022. Eight domestic, feral, or commensal mammal
364

365 species are recorded but only the latter are added to the native species list. Larger terrestrial
366 mammals were surveyed using over 780 camera traps deployed throughout NEOM to cover
367 diverse locations and representative habitats. Even with this substantial survey effort, four species
368 that once occurred (or may still occur) within NEOM were not detected. These are Arabian leopard
369 (*Panthera pardus nimr*), Dorcas gazelle (*Gazella dorcas*), Indian crested porcupine (*Hystrix*
370 *indica*), and Asiatic jackal (*Canis aureus*). Caracal (*Caracal caracal schmitzi*) were observed by
371 Saudi Wildlife Authority (now National Center for Wildlife) specialists at Jabal ad-Dibbagh and
372 near the Gulf of Aqaba shoreline at Ra's Suwayhil in 1989. Caracal has recently been detected
373 based on possible scat identification at two sites and the species has been documented to the north
374 and south of NEOM (Harrison & Bates, 1991; Eid et al., 2022). Dorcas gazelle may have occurred
375 in the alluvial fans in the northern Gulf of Aqaba as it still occurs in similar habitat in Jordan and
376 Egypt just across the Gulf. However, there is no evidence for Dorcas gazelle occurring today or in
377 the past in NEOM. Several gazelle specimens from the Haql area tested by the Saudi Wildlife
378 Authority (now National Center for Wildlife) were all Arabian gazelle (T. Wachter, pers. comm.
379 2025). Arabian leopard is known to have once occurred in the NEOM region (Islam et al., 2020).
380 The one record of a 'wild' Arabian gazelle detected through a 2022 camera-trap survey may be a
381 released individual from a local farm. However, wild Arabian gazelle were observed near the
382 Jordan border (currently within NEOM Nature Reserve) by National Center for Wildlife specialists
383 in the late 1980s (O A-a-R Llewellyn, pers. comm. 2025). Lion (*Panthera leo*), cheetah (*Acinonyx*
384 *jubatus*), Syrian wild ass (onager, *Equus hemionus x kulan*), Afri gazelle (*Gazella saudiya*, Saudi
385 Dorcas gazelle), and wild camel (*Camelus* sp.) were once part of the larger mammalian fauna but
386 were lost tens to hundreds of years ago (Harrison & Bates, 1991). Larger and medium-sized
387 mammalian carnivore richness is nine extant species—Arabian wolf (*Canis lupus arabs*), Arabian
388 red fox (*Vulpes vulpes arabica*), Blanford's fox (*Vulpes cana*), Rüppell's fox (*Vulpes rueppellii*),
389 striped hyena (*Hyaena hyaena*), wild cat (*Felis lybica lybica*), caracal (*Caracal caracal schmitzi*),
390 sand cat (*Felis margarita*), and honey badger (*Mellivora capensis*).

391

392 *Small mammals*

393 Fourteen native small mammal species have been recorded in NEOM. Different sets of species
394 commonly associated with several distinct habitat types occur. For example, gravel plains with
395 dense stands of dwarf shrub support Sundevall's and Libyan jirds (*Meriones crassus* and *Meriones*
396 *libycus*, respectively), several gerbils, and Arabian jerboa (*Jaculus loftusi*). High mountains and
397 wadis support Arabian spiny mouse (*Acomys dimidiatus*), golden spiny mouse (*Acomys russatus*),
398 bushy-tailed jird (*Sekeetamys calurus*), and Wagner's gerbils (*Gerbillus dasyurus*). Low altitude
399 mountain slopes and wadis support Arabian spiny mouse and Baluchistan gerbil (*Gerbillus nanus*).
400 The Hisma plateau supports several species, including fat sand rat (*Psammomys obesus*),
401 Cheesman's gerbil (*Gerbillus cheesmani*), golden spiny mouse, Arabian spiny mouse, gerbils, and
402 Asian garden dormouse (*Eliomys melanurus*). Cape hare (*Lepus capensis*), once numerous and
403 widespread, has declined significantly in recent decades (Mallon et al., 2023) and desert hedgehog
404 (*Paraechinus aethiopicus*) are relatively common through most habitats. The detection and
405 identification of shrew species is limited and requires further dedicated surveys, including analysis
406 of pellets from birds of prey, such as owls.

407

408 *Bats*

409 Several bat species occur at many localities throughout NEOM, including the naked-bellied tomb
410 bat (*Taphozous nudiventris*), Egyptian tomb bat (*Taphozous perforatus*), trident leaf-nosed bat

411 (*Asellia tridens*), Egyptian free-tailed bat (*Tadarida aegyptiaca*), European free-tailed bat
412 (*Tadarida teniotis*), Aden slit-faced bat (*Nycteris thebaica*), Egyptian fruit bat (*Rousettus*
413 *aegyptiacus*), lesser horseshoe (*Rhinolophus hipposideros*), Geoffroy's horseshoe (*Rhinolophus*
414 *clivosus*), Arabian mouse-tailed bat (*Rhinopoma cystops*), greater mouse-tailed bat (*Rhinopoma*
415 *microphyllum*), Arabian barbastelle (*Barbastella leucomelas*), Bottas serotine (*Eptesicus bottae*),
416 desert pipistrelle (*Hypsugo ariel*), desert long-eared bat (*Otonycteris hemprichii*), Christie's big-
417 eared bat (*Plecotus christii*), and Sind bat (*Rhyneptesicus nasutus*).

418
419 NEOM's surveys have documented in NEOM the 17 bat species confirmed to occur in the Prince
420 Mohammed bin Salman Royal Reserve (PMBSRR) that borders NEOM to the south (Haggon et
421 al., 2025). *Vansoni rueppellii* was also found in PMBSRR but has not yet been documented in
422 NEOM. There are nine species of bat that potentially be observed in NEOM but have not been
423 confirmed.

424
425 Further research is needed to confirm the species identity of eight bat species that have been
426 recorded acoustically or in hand but were not able to be confirmed to species level (Appendix B,
427 Table B5). Given the difficulties in determining bats from their echolocation, with limited call
428 references from the region, there is the potential for further bat species to be found within NEOM.

429
430

430 *Marine Mammals*

431 Seventeen species of marine mammal have been recorded in the Red Sea—16 species of cetacean
432 and one species of sirenian. Ten species of marine mammal are classified as being regular
433 occurrences or residents to the basin with several of these being recorded in NEOM. Four marine
434 mammal species are very regularly sighted in NEOM, namely Indian Ocean humpback dolphin
435 (*Sousa plumbea*), spinner dolphin (*Stenella longirostris*), Indo-Pacific bottlenose dolphin
436 (*Tursiops aduncus*), and dugong (*Dugong dugon*). Population numbers for each marine mammal
437 species in the Red Sea need further research and data to be accurately quantified. Aerial surveys
438 carried out by Preen (1989) estimated a population of ~1,800 dugongs in the Red Sea (see Nasr et
439 al., 2019). This population estimate, while dated, suggests that the Red Sea population is the third
440 largest in the world behind northeastern Australia and the Arabian Gulf. Population estimates of
441 dugong within NEOM are ongoing with unpublished surveys and community sightings of mother
442 and calf dugong pairs suggesting a small and breeding population. Sightings of Indian Ocean
443 humpback dolphin pods with young calves thought to be born in NEOM indicate that the area is
444 being used as a breeding and nursing ground for this threatened species. Ongoing research into the
445 spinner dolphin, Indo-Pacific bottlenose dolphin, and other marine mammal species frequenting
446 NEOM's waters will enhance further the understanding of these species.

447
448

448 *Birds*

449 Distribution maps that are included in Boland and Alsuhaibany (2020) suggested up to 316 bird
450 species could potentially occur at NEOM throughout the year. However, the range maps depicted
451 in Boland and Alsuhaibany (2020) were based on expert opinion, in a portion of Saudi Arabia that
452 was until now largely unsurveyed. The surveys conducted in the past few years far outweigh (by
453 orders of magnitude) our prior understanding of the species ranges within this region. In total, 308
454 bird species have been recorded since surveys began in 2021. The surveys have detected 100% of
455 the presumed resident species at NEOM. A further 23 species could potentially occur (see
456 Appendix B). None of these 23 species are resident but rather they are all rare migrants, including

457 rare to exceptionally rare passage migrants (including one species that may in fact be extinct) and
458 uncommon to very rare winter visitors. The fact that these 23 species have not been recorded
459 despite such exceptionally extensive survey effort suggests that the range maps in Boland and
460 Alsuhaibany (2020) need to be revised. Thus, the 308 species recorded to date within NEOM
461 represents *an absolute minimum* of 90% (n=283/316 possible species) of the potential bird species
462 diversity at NEOM but more likely represents 95-100% of all species likely to occur at NEOM.

463
464 The main gap in bird survey effort is seasonal. Relatively few surveys have been conducted in
465 winter compared to the exceptional survey efforts in spring and autumn. There are no obvious
466 taxonomic gaps in bird survey effort.

467
468 Most surveys have been conducted in the southern half of NEOM (apart from two years of survey
469 conducted at Haql in the extreme northwestern limit of the site). These surveys have been
470 conducted on the coasts, coastal plains, mountains, *harrat*, and Hisma desert at 309 separate
471 locations. Surveying the northern portion of the site would almost certainly not add any new bird
472 species to the inventory for two reasons: (i) every breeding resident species potentially occurring
473 in NEOM has already been recorded; (ii) the few remaining possible species not yet detected are
474 all migratory and just as likely to be recorded in the south as in the north. Thus, while there is a
475 ‘geographic gap’, filling this gap would likely add no additional species to the list.

476
477 Seventeen bird species previously listed as vagrants (recorded on less than 10 occasions in KSA:
478 *cf.* Boland & Alsuhaibany 2020) have been recorded in these surveys (Appendix B). These studies
479 suggest that many of these species should now be regarded as regular species in KSA. For example,
480 142 Lesser spotted eagles (*Clanga pomarina*) have now been recorded in the surveys, compared
481 to only six throughout the rest of Saudi Arabia (*cf.* [114]). In addition, 75 species are of global
482 (n=22 species), regional (n=28 species) or national (n=44 species) conservation concern (*cf.*
483 Boland & Burwell, 2020) (some species meet more than one criterion for listing).

484 *Reptiles & Amphibians*

485 Most of the herpetofauna species listed are known and well documented in surrounding areas (that
486 is, most of the species are shared with southern Jordan, other provinces of Saudi Arabia, some are
487 known also from Sinai Peninsula, the Palestine territories, and Israel) (Appendix B). Areas within
488 NEOM that appear comparatively rich in herpetofauna are the Hisma Desert and the volcanic fields
489 of Harrat ar Raha. Hisma Desert is part of the same geomorphological complex and shares most
490 of the known species with the Wadi Rum Protected Area in Jordan (Abu Baker et al., 2004).

491
492 *Stenodactylus sthenodactylus*, *Ptyodactylus guttatus*, *Platycephalus sinai*, and *Rhynchocalamus*
493 *hejazicus* are species previously not reported and recorded for the first time through the NEOM
494 surveys conducted since 2021 (see Egan et al., 2023; Pola et al., 2024; Licata et al., 2024).
495 *Telescopus hoogstraali*, *Rhynchocalamus melanocephalus*, and an undescribed species of
496 *Hemidactylus* are also new and will be discussed in detail elsewhere.

497
498
499 Despite hundreds of new records and dedicated herpetofauna surveys conducted since 2021, only
500 a small portion of NEOM has been touched as a vast part of its territory remains largely blank and
501 poorly explored in terms of species occurrence. Certain species remain known only from a handful

502 of records. Additional surveys are required to increase confidence in the completeness of the
503 species list.

504

505 *Marine Reptiles*

506 Five of the seven marine turtle species have been recorded in the Red Sea: Green Turtle (*Chelonia*
507 *mydas*), Hawksbill Turtle (*Eretmochelys imbricata*), Loggerhead Turtle (*Carretta caretta*), Olive
508 Ridley Turtle (*Lepidochelys olivacea*), and the Leatherback (*Dermochelys coriacea*). Only the
509 green and hawksbill have been recorded to successfully nest in the region. The Red Sea supports
510 globally significant numbers of both species, with NEOM being a key region for a large proportion
511 of the Red Sea's green and hawksbill nesting populations. Within NEOM, almost all the major
512 islands have marine turtle nesting records of both species, highlighting the high use of the area for
513 the animals. Nesting surveys have identified that the region is one of the most important for
514 hawksbills and green turtles in the northern Red Sea. The region's high density of coral reef and
515 seagrass habitats provides vital areas for the species in all life stages. Both species, sexes, and
516 multiple life stages of marine turtles can be sighted within NEOM. Tagging efforts within NEOM
517 have provided a valuable insight into the migratory, foraging, and general movement patterns of
518 both species, with some individuals travelling over 500 km. Previous studies (Mancini et al. 2019)
519 suggested that the northern Red Sea Green Turtle could have unique genetic units. However, to
520 confirm this, further samples and genetic studies need to be carried out (Mancini et al. 2019).

521

522 *Marine Fishes*

523 Golani and Fricke (2018) enumerated a total of 1,207 species distributed among 164 families in
524 the Red Sea and Gulf of Aqaba. The current checklist of fish for NEOM reports a total of 476
525 fishes distributed among 74 families. The marine fish identifications for NEOM are based on
526 published literature and NEOM and KAUST's collaborative fisheries program surveys, which
527 commenced in 2023 and include stock assessments, Baited Remote Underwater Videos, visual
528 census, and market surveys. Family Labridae (wrasses) is the most speciose taxa, represented by
529 63 species, followed by Pomacentridae (damselfishes; 41 species) and Gobiidae (gobies; 38
530 species). These three reef fish families, together, account for 29.8% of NEOM's marine fish
531 biodiversity. The total number of fish species listed, herein, is based on the best available
532 information. Given that there are at least 35 endemic species in the Gulf of Aqaba alone (DiBattista
533 et al., 2015, DiBattista et al., 2016, Fernandez-Silva et al., 2015, Golani & Fricke, 2018), it is
534 anticipated that more species will be added to the list after further study. This relatively high
535 number of endemics in such a small area suggests that isolation and other environmental or
536 biogeographic features may drive elevated speciation in the region. The presence of cryptic species
537 should be evaluated.

538

539 *Freshwater Fishes*

540 There are no native freshwater fish species documented from within NEOM (Krupp, 1983; Garcia
541 et al., 2015; Freyhoff et al., 2020). *Aphanius dispar* occurs in brackish water in coastal areas around
542 the Red Sea (Krupp, 1983), but this species has not been recorded in NEOM yet.

543

544 *Vascular Plants*

545 Despite its aridity, the richness of the flora of the NEOM area (587 confirmed species, Appendix
546 B) benefits from its geographical position. A good example of location affecting floral composition
547 can be taken from the Sinai Peninsula, situated roughly 17 km from NEOM on the opposite side

548 of Gulf of Aqaba west of NEOM. Despite making up only 6.1% of the area of Egypt, the area
549 holds 710 species. This is 56.2% of the total for Egypt (1,262) and 51% of the country's endemic
550 taxa (Boulos, 2008). South of NEOM, the Jabal Qaraqir mountain range (that slightly overlaps
551 NEOM), contains 160 different plant species (Al Abbasi et al., 2010). Jabal Qaraqir is the first of
552 many sites to be assessed as an Important Plant Area, designated as one of the most important
553 areas in the world for plant diversity. Immediately to the north of NEOM in Jordan is Wadi Rum,
554 within which an impressive 485 species have been recorded in a relatively small area (Borzatti von
555 Löwenstern et al., 2000). Thus, NEOM is surrounded by and shares flora with several notably
556 plant-rich regions.

557
558 NEOM lies at the junction between two major plant kingdoms, the Palaeotropic and the Holarctic.
559 This has substantial influence on species composition of the vegetation, which can change abruptly
560 over short distances, often in response to elevation. The two plant kingdoms comprise various
561 phytochoria, which differ in their interpretation amongst different vegetation scientists. According
562 to Léonard (1989), the following phytochoria relevant to NEOM can be differentiated, with a more
563 traditional classification in accordance with Takhtajan (1986) given in parentheses:

- 564
565 a. Arabian regional subzone of the Saharo-Sindian regional zone (= Saharo-Arabian region). This
566 region includes typical species of the Saharan and Arabian deserts, which occupy the interior of
567 NEOM, that is, usually away from the immediate near-coastal region.
- 568
569 b. Saharan regional subzone of the Saharo-Sindian regional zone (= Nubo-Sindian Province of the
570 Sudanian region). The species found here are also commonly referred to as 'Sudanian species',
571 and are characteristic of the subtropical savannas of Africa. In NEOM, and throughout large parts
572 of Arabia, they are mainly near-coastal, extending locally far inland.
- 573
574 c. Irano-Turanian regional center of endemism (= Irano-Turanian region). The species found here
575 are also referred to as 'Irano-Turanian species', ones that are typical of the north of Arabia (Syrian
576 desert / southern Turkey) extending eastwards through Iraq and Iran towards the Gobi Desert.
- 577
578 d. Mediterranean regional center of endemism (= Mediterranean region). These 'Mediterranean
579 species' are generally typical species of the Mediterranean Basin and, although some taxa occur
580 throughout NEOM, a number of others tend to be concentrated at the higher elevations.
- 581
582 e. Afromontane Archipelago-like regional center of endemism / Somalia-Masai regional center of
583 endemism (= Eritreo-Arabian Province of the Sudanian region). Such 'Afromontane species' are
584 characteristic of the Horn of Africa / south-west of Arabia and the mountains of east and north-
585 east Africa.

586
587 Species of the first and second categories account for a large proportion of the general flora of
588 NEOM, but in the context of the mountain peaks, the other three categories are of greater interest.
589 With respect to the fifth category (e), no taxa appear to be present in NEOM, although the genus
590 *Euryops*—represented in NEOM by *E. jaberiana*, which itself is very closely related to *E. arabicus*
591 (the latter can be assigned to the fifth category)—is Afromontane, but with most species occurring
592 in rocky areas in southern Africa rather than the Horn of Africa.

593

594 NEOM has populations of some exceptionally rare plant species, such as the Sinai primrose
595 (*Primula involucrata*) and Sinai wild rose (*Rosa arabica*). Both are restricted to the higher
596 elevations of Jibal al Lawz.

597

598 *NEOM's Species Richness*

599 The boundaries of the NEOM giga-project do not follow those of any recognized biogeographic
600 or physiographic unit (for example, Vincent [2008]). Rather, NEOM's boundaries cut across
601 ecosystem types, mountain ranges, lava plateaus (*harrat*), and distinct coastal marine ecosystems
602 (Fig. 1). Thus, the absence of whole biogeographic units precludes evaluating if the biota of NEOM
603 has an elevated richness compared to other biogeographic units of similar biogeographic resolution
604 (for example, ecoregions versus ecosystem types). However, two biogeographic features of
605 NEOM may promote elevated richness relative to that of surrounding regions. First, NEOM is
606 located within or near several major biogeographic realms (Palearctic, Afrotropical; see Dinerstein
607 et al., 2017), plant Kingdoms (Palearctic and Holarctic Plant Kingdoms) and Phytochoria (Brown
608 et al., 2023), and distinct marine units (for example, northern Red Sea and Gulf of Aqaba; Munro
609 et al., 2022). To illustrate, plant species characteristic of the Saharo-Arabian Phytochoria occupy
610 a large part of the interior of the Arabian Peninsula, whereas those of the Sudanian Phytochoria
611 are characteristic of the slightly climatically less extreme, near-coastal zone (Brown et al., 2023).
612 Elements of the Mediterranean and Irano-Turanian Phytochoria occur on the higher peaks of
613 NEOM. Thus, NEOM encompasses several assemblages of species characteristic of different
614 Phytochoria resulting in a rich mix of species and higher taxa representative of several distinct
615 biogeographic units. Second, NEOM's landscapes and seascapes display a broad range of
616 topographic and bathymetric environments and their associated ecosystems, from abyssal depths
617 and seagrass meadows to hyper-arid coastal plains, montane juniper groves, and sandstone buttes
618 surrounded by sand dunes and plains. The close proximity and rapid change with distance of these
619 environments, ecosystems, and species assemblages (for example, one can travel from 2,510 m to
620 -1,710 m in roughly 60 km) in NEOM contributes to high β and γ diversity that can further elevate
621 NEOM's species richness.

622

623 The distinctiveness of the biodiversity of the NEOM region is still being assessed, but, to date,
624 there are indications that several biodiversity features are of high biogeographic and conservation
625 interest. For example, the high peaks are considered bioclimatic refugia for multiple taxa on
626 account of the quite distinctive climatic conditions at such high elevations (mainly above *ca.* 1,750
627 m), which contrast markedly with the surrounding hot, arid conditions (Permanent Delegation of
628 the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to UNESCO, 2023). In addition, the sandstone pavement of the
629 Hisma Plateau has been identified as a globally rare habitat type (Sayre et al., 2014; Buro Happold
630 & Brown, 2022; Brown & Ayasrah, 2023). The close proximity of various ecosystems—coral and
631 seagrass nearshore marine ecosystems, coastal lowlands with acacia parklands, rugged granitic
632 mountains reaching over 2,500 m, the Hisma Desert with sandstone tablelands, and flood lava
633 plateaus (*harrat*)—contributes to regionally elevated β and γ diversity.

634

635 *Bioclimatic Refugia*

636 A suite of species on the native plant list and their occurrence on high peaks of NEOM, such as
637 *Nepeta glomerata*, *Tulipa biflora*, and *Sideritis montana* (Brown et al., 2023), lend support to the
638 inscription of NEOM's highest mountains on the World Heritage List as part of the “Bioclimatic
639 Refugia of Western Arabia” that function as bioclimatic refugia for multiple taxa (Permanent

640 Delegation of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to UNESCO, 2023). Ongoing investigations of high
641 elevation ants, butterflies, small mammals, and reptiles are evaluating the bioclimatic refugia
642 phenomenon for these taxa.

643
644 *Conclusion*

645 NEOM's biodiversity reflects the ecological complexity of northwest Saudi Arabia, encompassing
646 diverse habitats, such as coral reefs, seagrass meadows, arid deserts, and montane ecosystems.
647 These environments support a wide array of species, including a high number of endemics,
648 regionally significant taxa, and globally threatened species. Positioned along key migratory routes,
649 NEOM serves as a critical ecological corridor for avian and marine biota. This species inventory
650 forms a foundational reference for advancing ecological research and conservation strategies,
651 contributing to the protection and restoration of NEOM's ecosystems while aligning with global
652 biodiversity targets (e.g. 30x30, CBD 2024) and sustainable development frameworks.
653 Invertebrates remain a major gap in biodiversity knowledge for NEOM.

654
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668
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670
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673 contributions in early drafts of the manuscript. All were involved in field surveys for different taxa at
674 different times. Raneem Almalki prepared the maps and analyzed and synthesized the mammal data. All
675 other coauthors were actively involved in field surveys, species identification, literature review and
676 analysis, native species list compilation and review for their respective taxon, and contributions of taxon-
677 specific insights to the paper.

678
679 **Institutional Review Board Statement:** All surveys were conducted in accordance with the Guide for the
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681 of BioEthics - Third Edition) and, for surveys conducted by KAUST were conducted under the KAUST
682 Beacon Development's active research protocol and permit (22IACUC02) approved by the Institutional
683 Animal Care and Use Committee (the IACUC). NEOM and its contractors follow the guidelines outlined
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685
686

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693

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Appendix B. Species Lists of NEOM

Avifauna

Table B1. Native bird species recorded in NEOM as of December 2024. Species names follow IOC ver 14.2 (Gill et al., 2024).

Family name	Scientific name
Accipitridae	<i>Accipiter brevipes</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Accipiter nisus</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Aegypius monachus</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Aquila chrysaetos</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Aquila fasciata</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Aquila heliaca</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Aquila nipalensis</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Aquila verreauxii</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Buteo buteo vulpinus</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Buteo rufinus</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Circaetus gallicus</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Circus aeruginosus</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Circus cyaneus</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Circus macrourus</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Circus pygargus</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Clanga clanga</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Clanga pomarina</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Elanus caeruleus</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Gyps fulvus</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Hieraaetus pennatus</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Milvus migrans</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Neophron percnopterus</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Pernis apivorus</i>
Accipitridae	<i>Pernis ptilorhynchus</i>
Acrocephalidae	<i>Acrocephalus arundinaceus</i>
Acrocephalidae	<i>Acrocephalus palustris</i>
Acrocephalidae	<i>Acrocephalus schoenobaenus</i>
Acrocephalidae	<i>Acrocephalus scirpaceus</i>
Acrocephalidae	<i>Acrocephalus stentoreus</i>
Acrocephalidae	<i>Hippolais icterina</i>
Acrocephalidae	<i>Hippolais languida</i>
Acrocephalidae	<i>Hippolais olivetorum</i>
Acrocephalidae	<i>Iduna pallida</i>

Alaudidae	<i>Alaemon alaudipes</i>
Alaudidae	<i>Alauda arvensis</i>
Alaudidae	<i>Alaudala rufescens</i>
Alaudidae	<i>Ammomanes cinctura</i>
Alaudidae	<i>Ammomanes deserti</i>
Alaudidae	<i>Calandrella brachydactyla</i>
Alaudidae	<i>Eremalauda eremodites</i>
Alaudidae	<i>Eremophila bilopha</i>
Alaudidae	<i>Eremopterix nigriceps</i>
Alaudidae	<i>Galerida cristata</i>
Alaudidae	<i>Lullula arborea</i>
Alaudidae	<i>Melanocorypha bimaculata</i>
Alaudidae	<i>Ramphocoris clotbey</i>
Alcedinidae	<i>Alcedo atthis</i>
Alcedinidae	<i>Halycon smyrnensis</i>
Anatidae	<i>Anas acuta</i>
Anatidae	<i>Anas crecca</i>
Anatidae	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>
Anatidae	<i>Aythya ferina</i>
Anatidae	<i>Aythya nyroca</i>
Anatidae	<i>Mareca penelope</i>
Anatidae	<i>Spatula clypeata</i>
Anatidae	<i>Spatula querquedula</i>
Anatidae	<i>Tadorna tadorna</i>
Anatidae	<i>Tadorna ferruginea</i>
Apodidae	<i>Apus affinis</i>
Apodidae	<i>Apus apus</i>
Apodidae	<i>Apus pallidus</i>
Apodidae	<i>Ardea alba</i>
Ardeidae	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>
Ardeidae	<i>Ardea purpurea</i>
Ardeidae	<i>Ardeola ralloides</i>
Ardeidae	<i>Botaurus stellaris</i>
Ardeidae	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>
Ardeidae	<i>Butorides striata</i>
Ardeidae	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>
Ardeidae	<i>Egretta gularis</i>
Ardeidae	<i>Ixobrychus minutus</i>
Ardeidae	<i>Nycticorax nycticorax</i>
Ardeidae	<i>Tachymarptis melba</i>

Burhinidae	<i>Burhinus oedicephalus</i>
Caprimulgidae	<i>Caprimulgus aegyptius</i>
Caprimulgidae	<i>Caprimulgus europaeus</i>
Caprimulgidae	<i>Caprimulgus nubicus</i>
Charadriidae	<i>Charadrius asiaticus</i>
Charadriidae	<i>Anarhynchus atrifrons</i>
Charadriidae	<i>Charadrius alexandrinus</i>
Charadriidae	<i>Charadrius dubius</i>
Charadriidae	<i>Charadrius hiaticula</i>
Charadriidae	<i>Charadrius leschenaultii</i>
Charadriidae	<i>Eudromias morinellus</i>
Charadriidae	<i>Pluvialis apricaria</i>
Charadriidae	<i>Pluvialis fulva</i>
Charadriidae	<i>Pluvialis squatarola</i>
Charadriidae	<i>Vanellus spinosus</i>
Charadriidae	<i>Vanellus leucurus</i>
Charadriidae	<i>Vanellus vanellus</i>
Ciconiidae	<i>Ciconia ciconia</i>
Ciconiidae	<i>Ciconia nigra</i>
Cisticolidae	<i>Prinia gracilis</i>
Columbidae	<i>Columba livia</i>
Columbidae	<i>Columba oenas</i>
Columbidae	<i>Oena capensis</i>
Columbidae	<i>Spilopelia senegalensis</i>
Columbidae	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>
Columbidae	<i>Streptopelia roseogrisea</i>
Columbidae	<i>Streptopelia turtur</i>
Coraciidae	<i>Coracias garrulus</i>
Corvidae	<i>Corvus corone</i>
Corvidae	<i>Corvus rhipidurus</i>
Corvidae	<i>Corvus ruficollis</i>
Corvidae	<i>Corvus splendens</i>
Cuculidae	<i>Cuculus canorus</i>
Cuculidae	<i>Clamator glandarius</i>
Dromadidae	<i>Dromas ardeola</i>
Emberizidae	<i>Emberiza caesia</i>
Emberizidae	<i>Emberiza hortulana</i>
Emberizidae	<i>Emberiza striolata</i>
Estrildidae	<i>Euodice malabarica</i>
Falconidae	<i>Falco amurensis</i>

Falconidae	<i>Falco biarmicus</i>
Falconidae	<i>Falco columbarius</i>
Falconidae	<i>Falco concolor</i>
Falconidae	<i>Falco eleonora</i>
Falconidae	<i>Falco naumanni</i>
Falconidae	<i>Falco peregrinus</i>
Falconidae	<i>Falco subbuteo</i>
Falconidae	<i>Falco tinnunculus</i>
Falconidae	<i>Falco vespertinus</i>
Fringillidae	<i>Bucanetes githagineus</i>
Fringillidae	<i>Carpodacus synoicus</i>
Fringillidae	<i>Crithagra rothschildi</i>
Fringillidae	<i>Fringilla montifringilla</i>
Fringillidae	<i>Fringilla coelebs</i>
Fringillidae	<i>Rhodospiza obsoleta</i>
Fringillidae	<i>Serinus syriacus</i>
Glareolidae	<i>Cursorius cursor</i>
Glareolidae	<i>Glareola nordmanni</i>
Glareolidae	<i>Glareola pratincola</i>
Gruidae	<i>Grus grus</i>
Haematopodidae	<i>Haematopus ostralegus</i>
Hirundinidae	<i>Cecropis daurica</i>
Hirundinidae	<i>Delichon urbicum</i>
Hirundinidae	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>
Hirundinidae	<i>Ptyonoprogne obsoleta</i>
Hirundinidae	<i>Ptyonoprogne rupestris</i>
Hirundinidae	<i>Riparia riparia</i>
Hypocollidae	<i>Hypocolius ampelinus</i>
Laniidae	<i>Lanius collurio</i>
Laniidae	<i>Lanius excubitor</i>
Laniidae	<i>Lanius isabellinus</i>
Laniidae	<i>Lanius minor</i>
Laniidae	<i>Lanius nubicus</i>
Laniidae	<i>Lanius phoenicuroides</i>
Laniidae	<i>Lanius senator</i>
Laridae	<i>Chlidonias hybrida</i>
Laridae	<i>Chlidonias leucopterus</i>
Laridae	<i>Chroicocephalus genei</i>
Laridae	<i>Chroicocephalus ridibundus</i>
Laridae	<i>Gelochelidon nilotica</i>

Laridae	<i>Hydroprogne caspia</i>
Laridae	<i>Ichthyaetus hemprichii</i>
Laridae	<i>Ichthyaetus ichthyaetus</i>
Laridae	<i>Ichthyaetus leucophthalmus</i>
Laridae	<i>Larus armenicus</i>
Laridae	<i>Larus cachinnans</i>
Laridae	<i>Larus canus</i>
Laridae	<i>Larus michahellis</i>
Laridae	<i>Onychoprion anaethetus</i>
Laridae	<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>
Laridae	<i>Sterna hirundo</i>
Laridae	<i>Sterna repressa</i>
Laridae	<i>Sternula albifrons</i>
Laridae	<i>Sternula saundersi</i>
Laridae	<i>Thalasseus bengalensis</i>
Laridae	<i>Thalasseus bergii</i>
Laridae	<i>Thalasseus sandvicensis</i>
Leiotrichidae	<i>Argya squamiceps</i>
Locustellidae	<i>Locustella fluviatilis</i>
Locustellidae	<i>Locustella lucinioides</i>
Locustellidae	<i>Locustella naevia</i>
Meropidae	<i>Merops apiaster</i>
Meropidae	<i>Merops cyanophrys</i>
Meropidae	<i>Merops persicus</i>
Motacillidae	<i>Anthus campestris</i>
Motacillidae	<i>Anthus cervinus</i>
Motacillidae	<i>Anthus richardi</i>
Motacillidae	<i>Anthus spinoletta</i>
Motacillidae	<i>Anthus trivialis</i>
Motacillidae	<i>Motacilla alba</i>
Motacillidae	<i>Motacilla cinerea</i>
Motacillidae	<i>Motacilla citreola</i>
Motacillidae	<i>Motacilla flava</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Cercotrichas galactotes</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Cercotrichas podobe</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Ficedula albicollis</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Ficedula parva</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Ficedula semitorquata</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Irania gutturalis</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Luscinia luscinia</i>

Muscicapidae	<i>Luscinia megarhynchos</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Luscinia svecica</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Monticola saxatilis</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Monticola solitarius</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Muscicapa striata</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Oenanthe chrysopygia</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Oenanthe cypriaca</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Oenanthe deserti</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Oenanthe finschii</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Oenanthe hispanica</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Oenanthe isabellina</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Oenanthe leucopyga</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Oenanthe lugens</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Oenanthe melanura</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Oenanthe monacha</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Oenanthe oenanthe</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Oenanthe pleschanka</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Oenanthe xanthopygma</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Phoenicurus ochruros</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Phoenicurus phoenicurus</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Saxicola maurus</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Saxicola rubetra</i>
Nectariniidae	<i>Cinnyris osea</i>
Oriolidae	<i>Oriolus oriolus</i>
Pandionidae	<i>Pandion haliaetus</i>
Passeridae	<i>Carospiza brachydactyla</i>
Passeridae	<i>Gymnoris xanthocollis</i>
Passeridae	<i>Passer domesticus</i>
Passeridae	<i>Passer hispaniolensis</i>
Pelecanidae	<i>Pelecanus onocrotalus</i>
Phaethonidae	<i>Phaethon aethereus</i>
Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>
Phasianidae	<i>Alectoris chukar</i>
Phasianidae	<i>Ammoperdix heyi</i>
Phasianidae	<i>Coturnix coturnix</i>
Phoenicopteridae	<i>Phoenicopus roseus</i>
Phylloscopidae	<i>Phylloscopus collybita</i>
Phylloscopidae	<i>Phylloscopus inornatus</i>
Phylloscopidae	<i>Phylloscopus orientalis</i>
Phylloscopidae	<i>Phylloscopus sibilatrix</i>

Phylloscopidae	<i>Phylloscopus trochilus</i>
Picidae	<i>Jynx torquilla</i>
Podicipedidae	<i>Ardenna grisea</i>
Podicipedidae	<i>Podiceps nigricollis</i>
Procellariidae	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>
Pteroclididae	<i>Pterocles alchata</i>
Pteroclididae	<i>Pterocles coronatus</i>
Pteroclididae	<i>Pterocles orientalis</i>
Pteroclididae	<i>Pterocles senegallus</i>
Pycnonotidae	<i>Pycnonotus leucotis</i>
Pycnonotidae	<i>Pycnonotus xanthopygos</i>
Rallidae	<i>Crex crex</i>
Rallidae	<i>Fulica atra</i>
Rallidae	<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>
Rallidae	<i>Rallus aquaticus</i>
Rallidae	<i>Zapornia parva</i>
Rallidae	<i>Zapornia pusilla</i>
Recurvirostridae	<i>Himantopus himantopus</i>
Recurvirostridae	<i>Recurvirostra avosetta</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Actitis hypoleucos</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Arenaria interpres</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Calidris alba</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Calidris alpina</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Calidris canutus</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Calidris falcinellus</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Calidris ferruginea</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Calidris minuta</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Calidris pugnax</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Calidris temminckii</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Gallinago gallinago</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Gallinago media</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Limosa lapponica</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Limosa limosa</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Lymnocyptes minimus</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Numenius arquata</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Numenius phaeopus</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Tringa erythropus</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Tringa glareola</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Tringa nebularia</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Tringa ochropus</i>

Scolopacidae	<i>Tringa stagnatilis</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Tringa totanus</i>
Scolopacidae	<i>Xenus cinereus</i>
Scotocercidae	<i>Cettia cetti</i>
Scotocercidae	<i>Scotocerca inquieta</i>
Stercorariidae	<i>Stercorarius parasiticus</i>
Strigidae	<i>Asio flammeus</i>
Strigidae	<i>Asio otus</i>
Strigidae	<i>Athene noctua</i>
Strigidae	<i>Bubo ascalaphus</i>
Strigidae	<i>Otus brucei</i>
Strigidae	<i>Otus scops</i>
Struthionidae	<i>Struthio camelus</i> (reintroduced)
Sturnidae	<i>Onychognathus tristramii</i>
Sturnidae	<i>Pastor roseus</i>
Sturnidae	<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>
Sulidae	<i>Sula leucogaster</i>
Sylviidae	<i>Curruca cantillans</i>
Sylviidae	<i>Curucca communis</i>
Sylviidae	<i>Curruca conspicillata</i>
Sylviidae	<i>Curruca crassirostris</i>
Sylviidae	<i>Curruca curruca</i>
Sylviidae	<i>Curruca leucomelaena</i>
Sylviidae	<i>Curruca melanocephala</i>
Sylviidae	<i>Curruca melanothorax</i>
Sylviidae	<i>Curruca mystacea</i>
Sylviidae	<i>Curruca nana</i>
Sylviidae	<i>Curruca nisoria</i>
Sylviidae	<i>Curruca ruppeli</i>
Sylviidae	<i>Sylvia atricapilla</i>
Sylviidae	<i>Sylvia borin</i>
Threskiornithidae	<i>Platalea leucorodia</i>
Threskiornithidae	<i>Plegadis falcinellus</i>
Turdidae	<i>Turdus iliacus</i>
Turdidae	<i>Turdus philomelos</i>
Tytonidae	<i>Tyto alba</i>
Upupidae	<i>Upupa epops</i>

1409 **Possible Additional Bird Species**

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1411 **Table B2.** Additional bird species that could occur, based on expert opinion, in NEOM but have
1412 not yet been confirmed.

Asian Houbara – *Chlamydotis macqueenii*
Black Tern – *Chlidonias niger*
Cinereous Bunting – *Emberiza cineracea*
Common Linnet – *Linaria cannabina*
Eurasian Penduline-tit – *Remiz pendulinus*
European Goldfinch – *Carduelis carduelis*
Gadwall – *Mareca strepera*
Goliath Heron – *Ardea goliath*
Greylag Goose – *Anser anser*
Moustached Warbler – *Acrocephalus melanopogon*
Northern Bald Ibis – *Geronticus eremita*
Pied Avocet – *Recurvirostra avosetta*
Pied Kingfisher – *Ceryle rudis*
Pomarine Jaeger – *Stercorarius pomarinus*
Red-breasted Flycatcher – *Ficedula parva*
Red-crested Pochard – *Netta rufina*
Red-necked Phalarope – *Phalaropus lobatus*
Ruddy Shelduck – *Tadorna ferruginea*
Saker Falcon – *Falco cherrug*
Spotted Crake – *Porzana porzana*
Sociable Lapwing – *Vanellus gregarius*
Swinhoe's petrel – *Oceanodroma monorhis*
Tufted Duck – *Aythya fuligula*

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1414 **Vagrant Bird Species**

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1416 **Table B3.** Vagrant birds observed in NEOM from 2019 to December 2024.

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Species
Amur Falcon – *Falco amurensis*
Black-legged Kittiwake – *Rissa tridactyla*
Carrion Crow – *Corvus corone*
Cetti's Warbler – *Cettia cetti*
Collared Flycatcher – *Ficedula albicollis*
Cyprus Warbler – *Sylvia melanothorax*
Eastern Bonelli's Warbler – *Phylloscopus orientalis*
Eleonora's Falcon – *Falco eleonora*
Lesser Spotted Eagle – *Clanga pomarina*
Northern Long-eared Owl – *Asio otus*
Red Knot – *Calidris canutus*
Red-footed Falcon – *Falco vespertinus*
Richard's Pipit – *Anthus richardi*
River Warbler – *Locustella fluviatilis*
Sooty Shearwater – *Ardenna grisea*
Spectacled Warbler – *Curruca conspicillata*
Stock Dove – *Columba oenas*

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1420 **Mammals**

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1422 **Table B4.** Mammal species documented to occur in NEOM as of December 2024.

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Family	Species
Bovidae	<i>Capra nubiana</i>
	<i>Gazella arabica</i>
	<i>Gazella marica</i>
	<i>Oryx leucoryx</i>
Dugongidae	<i>Dugong dugon</i>
Delphinidae	<i>Grampus griseus</i>
	<i>Pseudorca crassidens</i>
	<i>Sousa plumbea</i>
	<i>Stenella attenuata</i>
	<i>Stenella longirostris</i>
	<i>Tursiops aduncus</i>
	<i>Tursiops truncatus</i>
Canidae	<i>Canis lupus arabs</i>
	<i>Vulpes cana</i>
	<i>Vulpes rueppellii</i>
	<i>Vulpes vulpes arabica</i>
Dipodidae	<i>Jaculus loftusi</i>
Emballonuridae	<i>Taphozous nudiventris</i>
	<i>Taphozous perforatus</i>
Erinaceidae	<i>Paraechinus aethiopicus</i>
Felidae	<i>Caracal caracal schmitzi</i>
	<i>Felis margarita</i>
	<i>Felis lybica lybica</i>
Gliridae	<i>Eliomys melanurus</i>
Hipposideridae	<i>Asellia tridens</i>
Hyaenidae	<i>Hyaena hyaena sultana</i>
Leporidae	<i>Lepus capensis</i>
Molossidae	<i>Tadarida aegyptiaca</i>
	<i>Tadarida teniotis</i>
Muridae	<i>Acomys dimidiatus</i>
	<i>Acomys russatus</i>
	<i>Gerbillus cheesmani</i>
	<i>Gerbillus dasyurus</i>
	<i>Gerbillus nanus</i>
	<i>Meriones crassus</i>
	<i>Meriones libycus</i>
	<i>Mus musculus</i>
	<i>Psammomys obesus</i>

	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	
	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	
	<i>Sekeetamys calurus</i>	
Mustellidae	<i>Mellivora capensis</i>	
Nycteridae	<i>Nycteris thebaica</i>	
Proaviidae	<i>Proavia capensis</i>	
Pteropodidae	<i>Rousettus aegyptiacus</i>	
Rhinolophidae	<i>Rhinolophus hipposideros</i>	
	<i>Rhinolophus clivosus</i>	
Rhinopomatidae	<i>Rhinopoma cystops</i>	
	<i>Rhinopoma microphyllum</i>	
Soricidae	<i>Crocidura suaveolens</i>	High likelihood this species
Vespertilionidae	<i>Barbastella leucomelas</i>	
	<i>Eptesicus bottae</i>	
	<i>Hypsugo ariel</i>	
	<i>Otonycteris hemprichii</i>	
	<i>Plecotus christii</i>	
	<i>Rhyneptesicus nasutus</i>	

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Table B5. Bats potentially observed in NEOM, but species identity not yet confirmed as of December 2024 and bats that are likely to occur but have not yet been detected.

Family	Species
Rhinolophidae	<i>Rhinolophus blasii</i>
	<i>Rhinolophus euryale</i>
	<i>Rhinolophus ferrumequinum</i>
	<i>Rhinolophus mehelyi</i>
Vespertilionidae	<i>Hypsugo arabicus</i>
	<i>Hypsugo savii</i>
	<i>Myotis</i> sp.
	<i>Pipistrellus kuhlii</i>
	<i>Vansonia rueppellii</i>

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Table B6. Non-bat mammal species once occurred (or possibly occurring) in NEOM

Family	Species
Balaenopteridae	<i>Balaenoptera edeni</i>
	<i>Balaenoptera omurai</i>
	<i>Balaenoptera musculus</i>
	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>
	<i>Gazella dorcas</i>
Bovidae	<i>Canis aureus</i>
Canidae	<i>Panthera pardus nimr</i>
Felidae	<i>Herpestes ichneumon</i>
Herpestidae	<i>Hystrix indica</i>
Hystriidae	

Muridae *Gerbillus henleyi*

Table B7. Mammal species extinct in NEOM.

Family	Species name
Camelidae	<i>Camelus dromedarius</i> (extinct wild form)
Equidae	<i>Equus hemionus x kulan</i>
Felidae	<i>Panthera leo</i>
Felidae	<i>Acinonyx jubatus</i>

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1430 **Table B8.** Domestic, Feral, and Commensal Mammal Species in NEOM as of December 2024.

Family	Species Name
Bovidae	<i>Capra hircus</i>
	<i>Ovis aries</i>
Camelidae	<i>Camelus dromedarius</i>
Canidae	<i>Canis familiaris</i>
Equidae	<i>Equus caballus</i>
	<i>Equus africanus asinus</i>
Felidae	<i>Felis catus</i>
1431 Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>
1432	<i>Rattus rattus</i>
1433	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>

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Reptiles & Amphibians

Table B9. Reptile and amphibian native species documented for NEOM as of December 2024.

Family	Species	Notes
Agamidae	<i>Laudakia vulgaris</i>	previously <i>Stellagama</i>
	<i>Phrynocephalus arabicus</i>	
	<i>Pseudotrapelus aqabensis</i>	
	<i>Pseudotrapelus sinaitus</i>	
	<i>Trapelus agnetae</i>	
	<i>Uromastyx aegyptia</i>	
	<i>Uromastyx ornata</i>	
Atractaspidae	<i>Atractaspis engaddensis</i>	
Bufonidae	<i>Sclerophrys arabica</i>	
Chamaeleonidae	<i>Chamaeleo chamaeleon orientalis</i>	
Cheloniidae	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	
	<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	
Colubridae	<i>Lytorhynchus diadema</i>	
	<i>Platycephs elegantissimus</i>	
	<i>Platycephs rhodorachis</i>	
	<i>Platycephs saharicus</i>	previously <i>P. rhodorachis</i>
	<i>Platycephs sinai</i>	
	<i>Rhynchocalamus hejazicus</i>	
	<i>Rhynchocalamus melanocephalus</i>	
	<i>Spalerosophis diadema cliffordii</i>	
	<i>Telescopus dhara</i>	
	<i>Telescopus hoogstraali</i>	pending DNA confirmation
Elapidae	<i>Walterinnesia aegyptia</i>	
Boidae	<i>Eryx jaculus</i>	
Gekkonidae	<i>Bunopus tuberculatus</i>	
	<i>Cyrtopodion scabrum</i>	
	<i>Hemidactylus mindiae</i>	
	<i>Hemidactylus</i> sp. (<i>saba</i> group)	likely an undescribed species of <i>Hemidactylus saba</i> group
	<i>Stenodactylus doriae</i>	
	<i>Stenodactylus slevini</i>	
	<i>Stenodactylus sthenodactylus</i>	
	<i>Trigonodactylus arabicus</i>	
	<i>Tropicolotes nattereri</i>	
	<i>Tropicolotes yomtovi</i>	
Lacertidae	<i>Acanthodactylus boskianus</i>	
	<i>Acanthodactylus hardyi</i>	
	<i>Acanthodactylus opheodurus</i>	
	<i>Acanthodactylus schmidtii</i>	
	<i>Acanthodactylus tilburyi</i>	

	<i>Mesalina bahaeldini</i>	
	<i>Mesalina bernoullii</i>	
	<i>Ophisops elegans</i>	literature record without additional evidence; unpublished record in preparation
	<i>Phoenicolacerta kulzeri</i> ssp.	
Leptotyphlopidae	<i>Myriopholis nursii</i>	Photographed, most likely the species, but DNA would be needed to confirm
	<i>Myriopholis macrorhyncha</i>	Poorly photographed, no DNA sample taken
Phyllodactylidae	<i>Ptyodactylus</i> cf. <i>ananjevae</i>	
	<i>Ptyodactylus guttatus</i>	
	<i>Ptyodactylus hasselquistii</i>	
Psammophiidae	<i>Malpolon moilensis</i>	
	<i>Psammophis schokari</i>	
Scincidae	<i>Scincus scincus meccensis</i>	
	<i>Eumeces schneiderii</i>	
	<i>Chalcides ocellatus</i>	
	<i>Trachylepis brevicollis</i>	
Sphaerodactylidae	<i>Pristurus guweirensis</i>	previously <i>Pristurus rupestris</i>
Trogonophidae	<i>Diplometopon zarudnyi</i>	
Varanidae	<i>Varanus griseus griseus</i>	
Viperidae	<i>Cerastes gasperettii gasperetti</i>	
	<i>Echis coloratus coloratus</i>	

1438
1439 **Table B10.** Native reptile and amphibian species reported in vicinity but not yet confirmed during
1440 the recent efforts within NEOM.
1441

1442	Family	Species	Notes
1443	Agamidae	<i>Trapelus ruderatus</i>	
		<i>Trapelus flavimaculatus</i>	
	Bufo	<i>Bufo sitibundus</i>	Possible tadpole observed in Wadi Tayyib Ism (G. Feulner, pers. comm. 2024)
	Cheloniidae	<i>Caretta caretta</i>	
		<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	
	Dermochelyidae	<i>Dermochelys coriacea</i>	
	Gekkonidae	<i>Hemidactylus flaviviridis</i>	
		<i>Hemidactylus granosus</i>	
	Scincidae	<i>Eurylepis taeniolatus</i>	

1444
1445 **Table B11.** Native reptile species reported previously but that are unlikely to occur within NEOM.
1446

Family	Species
Agamidae	<i>Phrynocephalus longicaudatus</i>
	<i>Trapelus persicus</i>
Boidae	<i>Eryx jayakari</i>
Bufo	<i>Duttaphrynus dhufarensis</i>
Colubridae	<i>Eirenis coronella</i>

Gekkonidae	<i>Hemidactylus robustus</i> <i>Hemidactylus turcicus</i> <i>Stenodactylus grandiceps</i>
Hylidae	<i>Hyla felixarabica</i> <i>Hyla savignyi</i>
Lacertidae	<i>Acanthodactylus grandis</i> <i>Acanthodactylus robustus</i> <i>Acanthodactylus scutellatus</i> <i>Mesalina olivieri</i>
Scincidae	<i>Ablepharus rueppellii</i> <i>Chalcides sepsoides</i> <i>Scincus mitranus</i>
Sphaerodactylidae	<i>Pristurus flavipunctatus</i>
Viperidae	<i>Pseudocerastes fieldi</i>

1447

1448 **Marine Fishes**

1449

1450 **Table B12.** Marine fishes of NEOM waters as of December 2024.

1451

1452

Family	Species
Acanthuridae	<i>Acanthurus gahhm</i>
	<i>Acanthurus mata</i>
	<i>Acanthurus nigricans</i>
	<i>Acanthurus nigrofuscus</i>
	<i>Acanthurus sohal</i>
	<i>Ctenochaetus striatus</i>
	<i>Naso brevirostris</i>
	<i>Naso elegans</i>
	<i>Naso hexacanthus</i>
	<i>Naso lituratus</i>
	<i>Naso unicornis</i>
	<i>Zebrasoma desjardinii</i>
	<i>Zebrasoma velifer</i>
<i>Zebrasoma xanthurum</i>	
Aetobatidae	<i>Aetobatus narinari</i>
	<i>Aetobatus ocellatus</i>
Alopiidae	<i>Alopias pelagicus</i>
Aploactinidae	<i>Ptarmus gallus</i>
Apogonidae	<i>Pristiapogon kallopterus</i>
Apogonidae	<i>Apogon aureus</i>
	<i>Apogon fleurieu</i>
	<i>Apogonichthyoides heptastygma</i>
	<i>Archamia bilineata</i>
	<i>Cheilodipterus arabicus</i>
	<i>Cheilodipterus lachneri</i>
	<i>Cheilodipterus macrodon</i>
	<i>Cheilodipterus novemstriatus</i>
	<i>Cheilodipterus pygmaios</i>
	<i>Cheilodipterus quinquelineatus</i>
	<i>Ostorhinchus cyanosoma</i>
	<i>Ostorhinchus nigrofasciatus</i>
	<i>Pristiapogon fraenatus</i>
	<i>Pristiapogon exostigma</i>
	<i>Rhabdamia nigrimentum</i>
	<i>Siphamia tubifer</i>
<i>Taeniamia fucata</i>	
<i>Verulux cypselurus</i>	
Balistidae	<i>Balistapus undulatus</i>
	<i>Balistes viridescens</i>
	<i>Balistoides viridescens</i>

	<i>Odonus niger</i>
	<i>Pseudobalistes flavimarginatus</i>
	<i>Pseudobalistes fuscus</i>
	<i>Rhinecanthus assasi</i>
	<i>Sufflamen albicaudatum</i>
	<i>Sufflamen albicaudatus</i>
Belonidae	<i>Tylosurus choram</i>
Blennidae	<i>Alloblennius pictus</i>
	<i>Aspidontus dussumieri</i>
	<i>Aspidontus taeniatus</i>
	<i>Atrosalarias fuscus</i>
	<i>Cirripectes castaneus</i>
	<i>Escenius aroni</i>
	<i>Ecsenius dentex</i>
	<i>Escenius frontalis</i>
	<i>Escenius graviera</i>
	<i>Escenius midas</i>
	<i>Enchelyurus petersi</i>
	<i>Meiacanthus nigrolineatus</i>
	<i>Exallias brevis</i>
	<i>Mimoblennius cirrosus</i>
	<i>Petroscirtes mitratus</i>
	<i>Plagiotremus rhinorhynchos</i>
	<i>Plagiotremus tapeinosoma</i>
	<i>Plagiotremus townsendi</i>
	<i>Salarias fasciatus</i>
	<i>Xiphasia setifer</i>
Bothidae	<i>Bothus pantherinus</i>
Caesionidae	<i>Caesio caerulea</i>
	<i>Caesio lunaris</i>
	<i>Caesio stiratus</i>
	<i>Caesio suevica</i>
	<i>Caesio varilineata</i>
	<i>Pterocaesio chrysozona</i>
Callionymidae	<i>Diplogrammus randalli</i>
Carangidae	<i>Alepes djedaba</i>
	<i>Alepes vari</i>
	<i>Atule mate</i>
	<i>Carangoides bajad</i>
	<i>Carangoides ferdau</i>
	<i>Carangoides fulvoguttatus</i>
	<i>Caranx ignobilis</i>
	<i>Caranx melampygus</i>
	<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i>

	<i>Scomberoides lysan</i>
	<i>Selar crumenophthalmus</i>
	<i>Seriola dumerili</i>
Carcharhinidae	<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i>
	<i>Carcharhinus brevipinna</i>
	<i>Carcharhinus falciformis</i>
	<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i>
	<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>
	<i>Carcharhinus plumbeus</i>
	<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>
Centriscidae	<i>Aeoliscus punctulatus</i>
Chaetodontidae	<i>Chaetodon auriga</i>
	<i>Chaetodon austriacus</i>
	<i>Chaetodon fasciatus</i>
	<i>Chaetodon larvatus</i>
	<i>Chaetodon lineolatus</i>
	<i>Chaetodon melannotus</i>
	<i>Chaetodon melapterus</i>
	<i>Chaetodon mesoleucos</i>
	<i>Chaetodon paucifasciatus</i>
	<i>Chaetodon pictus</i>
	<i>Chaetodon semilarvatus</i>
	<i>Chaetodon trifascialis</i>
	<i>Heniochus dipheurtes</i>
	<i>Heniochus intermedius</i>
Chanidae	<i>Chanos chanos</i>
Cirrhitidae	<i>Cirrhitichthys oxycephalus</i>
	<i>Cirrhites calliurus</i>
	<i>Cirrhites pinnulatus</i>
	<i>Paracirrhites forsteri</i>
	<i>Oxycirrhites typus</i>
Congridae	<i>Gorgasia sillneri</i>
Dasyatidae	<i>Himantura fai</i>
	<i>Himantura uarnak</i>
	<i>Taeniura lymma</i>
	<i>Taeniura meyeni</i>
Diodontidae	<i>Cyclichthys spilostylus</i>
	<i>Diodon holocanthus</i>
	<i>Diodon hystrix</i>
	<i>Diodon liturosus</i>
Dorosomatidae	<i>Herklotsichthys punctatus</i>
Dussumieriidae	<i>Etrumeus sadina</i>
Echeneidae	<i>Echeneis naucrates</i>
Ephippidae	<i>Platax boersii</i>

	<i>Platax orbicularis</i>
Fistulariidae	<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>
Gerreidae	<i>Gerres longirostris</i>
	<i>Gerres oyena</i>
Glaucostegidae	<i>Glaucostegus halavi</i>
Gobiidae	<i>Amblyeleotris steinitzi</i>
	<i>Amblyeleotris sungami</i>
	<i>Amblygobius albimaculatus</i>
	<i>Amblygobius nocturnus</i>
	<i>Amblygobius sewardii</i>
	<i>Asterropteryx semipunctata</i>
	<i>Bryaninops natans</i>
	<i>Cryptocentrus caeruleopunctatus</i>
	<i>Cryptocentrus lutheri</i>
	<i>Ctenogobiops crocineus</i>
	<i>Ctenogobiops maculosus</i>
	<i>Eviota guttata</i>
	<i>Eviota marerubrum</i>
	<i>Eviota punyit</i>
	<i>Eviota sebrei</i>
	<i>Eviota zebrina</i>
	<i>Exyrias belisimus</i>
	<i>Fusigobius humeralis</i>
	<i>Fusigobius maximus</i>
	<i>Fusigobius neophytus</i>
	<i>Gnatholepis anjerensis</i>
	<i>Gnatholepis caudimaculata</i>
	<i>Gobiodon citrinus</i>
	<i>Gobiodon prolixus</i>
	<i>Gobiodon rivulatus</i>
	<i>Heteroleotris psammophila</i>
	<i>Istigobius decoratus</i>
	<i>Koumansetta hectori</i>
	<i>Koumansetta hoesei</i>
	<i>Lotilia graciliosa</i>
	<i>Macrodontogobius wilburi</i>
	<i>Pleurosicya mossambica</i>
	<i>Tomiyamichthys latruncularius</i>
	<i>Trimma avidori</i>
	<i>Trimma flavicaudatum</i>
	<i>Valenciennea puellaris</i>
	<i>Valenciennea sexguttata</i>
	<i>Vanderhorstia delagoae</i>
Haemulidae	<i>Diagramma pictum</i>

	<i>Diagramma punctatum</i>
	<i>Plectorhincus albovittatus</i>
	<i>Plectorhinchus gaterinus</i>
	<i>Plectorhincus gibbosus</i>
	<i>Plectorhinchus pictus</i>
	<i>Plectorhincus playfairi</i>
	<i>Plectorhincus schotaf</i>
	<i>Plectorhincus sordidus</i>
	<i>Pomadasys stridens</i>
Hemiramphidae	<i>Hemiramphus far</i>
Holocentridae	<i>Myripristis murdjan</i>
	<i>Neoniphon sammara</i>
	<i>Sargocentron caudimaculatum</i>
	<i>Sargocentron diadema</i>
	<i>Sargocentron rubrum</i>
	<i>Sargocentron spiniferum</i>
Kyphosidae	<i>Kyphosus bigibbus</i>
	<i>Kyphosus cinerascens</i>
	<i>Kyphosus vaigiensis</i>
Labridae	<i>Anampses caeruleopunctatus</i>
	<i>Anampses lineatus</i>
	<i>Anampses meleagrides</i>
	<i>Anampses twistii</i>
	<i>Bodianus anthioides</i>
	<i>Bodianus axillaris</i>
	<i>Bodianus diana</i>
	<i>Cheilinus abudjubbe</i>
	<i>Cheilinus diagrammus</i>
	<i>Cheilinus fasciatus</i>
	<i>Cheilinus lunulatus</i>
	<i>Cheilinus mentalis</i>
	<i>Cheilinus quinquecinctus</i>
	<i>Cheilinus trilobatus</i>
	<i>Cheilinus undulatus</i>
	<i>Chelio inermis</i>
	<i>Cirrhilabrus blatteus</i>
	<i>Cirrhilabrus rubriventralis</i>
	<i>Coris aygula</i>
	<i>Coris caudimacula</i>
	<i>Coris cuvieri</i>
	<i>Coris formosa</i>
	<i>Coris variegata</i>
	<i>Epibulus insidiator</i>
	<i>Gomphosus klunzingeri</i>

Halichoeres hortulanus
Halichoeres iridus
Halichoeres nebulosus
Halichoeres marginatus
Halichoeres scapularis
Halichoeres zeylonicus
Hemigymnus fasciatus
Hemigymnus melapterus
Hemigymnus sexfasciatus
Hologymnosus annulatus
Hologymnosus doliatus
Iniistius pavo
Iniistius pentadactylus
Labroides bicolor
Labroides dimidiatus
Larabicus quadrilineatus
Macropharyngodon bipartitus
Macropharyngodon marisrubri
Minilabrus striatus
Novaculichthys taeniourus
Oxycheilinus digramma
Oxycheilinus mentalis
Paracheilinus octotaenia
Pseudocheilinus evanidus
Pseudocheilinus hexataenia
Pseudodax moluccanus
Pteragogus cryptus
Pteragogus pelycus
Thalassoma rueppellii
Thalassoma lunare
Oxycheilinus diagrammus
Oxycheilinus orientalis
Stethojulis albovittata
Stethojulis interrupta
Thalassoma lutescens
Thalassoma mahsena
Thalassoma purpureum
Thalassoma rueppelli
Gymnocranius grandoculis
Lethrinus borbonicus
Lethrinus harak
Lethrinus lentjan
Lethrinus mahsena
Lethrinus microdon

Lethrinidae

	<i>Lethrinus nebulosus</i>
	<i>Lethrinus obsoletus</i>
	<i>Lethrinus olivaceus</i>
	<i>Lethrinus variegatus</i>
	<i>Lethrinus xanthochilus</i>
	<i>Monotaxis ehrenbergi</i>
	<i>Monotaxis grandoculis</i>
Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus argentimaculatus</i>
	<i>Lutjanus bohar</i>
	<i>Lutjanus bohar</i>
	<i>Lutjanus ehrenbergi</i>
	<i>Lutjanus fulviflamma</i>
	<i>Lutjanus gibbus</i>
	<i>Lutjanus kasmira</i>
	<i>Lutjanus monostigma</i>
	<i>Lutjanus rivulatus</i>
	<i>Macolor niger</i>
Malacanthidae	<i>Malacanthus brevirostris</i>
	<i>Malacanthus latovittatus</i>
Microdesmidae	<i>Ptereleotris evides</i>
Microdesmidae	<i>Nemateleotris decora</i>
Mobulidae	<i>Mobula alfredi</i>
	<i>Mobula birostris</i>
Monacanthidae	<i>Aluterus scriptus</i>
	<i>Anamses scopas</i>
	<i>Cantherhinus pardalis</i>
	<i>Oxymonacanthus halli</i>
	<i>Paraluteres arqat</i>
	<i>Pervagor randalli</i>
	<i>Stephanolepis diaspros</i>
Mugilidae	<i>Plicomugil labiosus</i>
Mullidae	<i>Mulloidichthys flavolineatus</i>
	<i>Mulloidichthys vanicolensis</i>
	<i>Parupenrus cyclostomus</i>
	<i>Parupeneus forsskali</i>
	<i>Parupeneus macronemus</i>
	<i>Parupeneus margaritatus</i>
	<i>Parupeneus macronemus</i>
	<i>Parupeneus rubescens</i>
Muraenidae	<i>Gymnothorax flavimarginatus</i>
	<i>Gymnothorax griseus</i>
	<i>Gymnothorax javanicus</i>
	<i>Gymnothorax nudivomer</i>
	<i>Gymnothorax undulatus</i>

Nemipteridae	<i>Scolopsis ghanam</i>	
	<i>Scolopsis imaculatus</i>	
	<i>Scolopsis taeniata</i>	
	<i>Scolopsis vosmeri</i>	
Ophichthidae	<i>Myrichthys colubrinus</i>	
	<i>Myrichthys maculosus</i>	
Ostraciidae	<i>Ostracion cubicum</i>	
	<i>Ostracion cyanurus</i>	
	<i>Ostracion imperator</i>	
	<i>Ostracion meleagris</i>	
Pempheridae	<i>Parapriacanthus guentheri</i>	
	<i>Pempheris nesogallica</i>	
	<i>Pempheris oualensis</i>	
	<i>Pempheris schwenkii</i>	
	<i>Pempheris tominagai</i>	
	<i>Pempheris vanicolensis</i>	
Pinguipedidae	<i>Parapercis hexophtalma</i>	
Platycephalidae	<i>Papilloculiceps longiceps</i>	
Plotosidae	<i>Plotosus lineatus</i>	
Pomacanthidae	<i>Apolemichthys xanthotis</i>	
	<i>Centropyge multispinis</i>	
	<i>Genicanthus caudovittatus</i>	
	<i>Pomacanthus asfur</i>	
	<i>Pomacanthus imperator</i>	
	<i>Pomacanthus maculosus</i>	
	<i>Pomacanthus sexfasciatus</i>	
	<i>Pygoplites diacanthus</i>	
	Pomacentridae	<i>Abudefduf aquilis</i>
		<i>Abudefduf indicus</i>
<i>Abudefduf flavilatus</i>		
<i>Abudefduf sexfasciatus</i>		
<i>Abudefduf sordidus</i>		
<i>Abudefduf vaigiensis</i>		
<i>Amblyglyphidodon flavilatus</i>		
<i>Amblyglyphidodon indicus</i>		
<i>Amblyglyphidodon lacrymatus</i>		
<i>Amblyglyphidodon leucogaster</i>		
<i>Amblyglyphidodon sulfureus</i>		
<i>Amphiprion bicinctus</i>		
<i>Chromis dimidiata</i>		
<i>Chromis flavaxilla</i>		
<i>Chromis pelloura</i>		
<i>Chromis pembae</i>		
<i>Chromis trialpha</i>		

	<i>Chromis viridis</i>
	<i>Chromis weberi</i>
	<i>Chrysiptera annulata</i>
	<i>Chrysiptera unimaculata</i>
	<i>Dascyllus abudafur</i>
	<i>Dascyllus aruanus</i>
	<i>Dascyllus marginatus</i>
	<i>Dascyllus trimaculatus</i>
	<i>Neoglyphidodon melas</i>
	<i>Neopomacentrus cyanomos</i>
	<i>Neopomacentrus miryae</i>
	<i>Neopomacentrus xanthurus</i>
	<i>Paraglyphidodon melas</i>
	<i>Plectroglyphidodon lacrymatus</i>
	<i>Plectroglyphidodon leucozonus</i>
	<i>Pomacentrus albicaudatus</i>
	<i>Pomacentrus aquilus</i>
	<i>Pomacentrus leptus</i>
	<i>Pomacentrus sulfureus</i>
	<i>Pomacentrus trichourus</i>
	<i>Pomacentrus trilineatus</i>
	<i>Pristotis cyanostigma</i>
	<i>Stegastes lacrymatus</i>
	<i>Stegastes nigricans</i>
Priacanthidae	<i>Priacanthus hamrur</i>
Pseudochromidae	<i>Pseudochromis dixurus</i>
	<i>Pseudochromis flavivertex</i>
	<i>Pseudochromis fridmani</i>
	<i>Pseudochromis olivaceus</i>
	<i>Pseudochromis pesi</i>
	<i>Pseudochromis springeri</i>
Ptereleotridae	<i>Ptereleotris heteroptera</i>
Rhincodontidae	<i>Rhincodon typus</i>
Rhinidae	<i>Rhina ancylostomus</i>
	<i>Rhynchobatus djiddensis</i>
Scaridae	<i>Bolbometopon muricatum</i>
	<i>Calotomus viridescens</i>
	<i>Cetoscarus bicolor</i>
	<i>Chlorurus genozonatus</i>
	<i>Chlorurus gibbus</i>
	<i>Chlorurus sordidus</i>
	<i>Hipposcarus harid</i>
	<i>Leptoscarus vaigiensis</i>
	<i>Scarus collana</i>

Scarus falcipinnis
Scarus ferrugineus
Scarus frenatus
Scarus fuscopurpureus
Scarus ghobban
Scarus niger
Scarus psittacus
Scarus scaber
Scombridae *Rastrelliger kanagurta*
Scomberomorus commerson
Scorpaenidae *Inimicus filamentosus*
Pterois cincta
Pterois miles
Pterois radiata
Scorpaenopsis barbata
Scorpaenopsis diabolus
Scorpaenopsis oxycephalus
Sebastapistes cyanostigma
Serranidae *Aethaloperca rogae*
Anyperodon leucogrammicus
Cephalopholis argus
Cephalopholis hemistiktos
Cephalopholis miniata
Cephalopholis oligosticta
Cephalopholis sexmaculata
Diploprion drachi
Epinephelus areolatus
Epinephelus chlorostigma
Epinephelus coeruleopunctatus
Epinephelus fasciatus
Epinephelus fuscoguttatus
Epinephelus gabriellae
Epinephelus geoffroyi
Epinephelus leucogrammicus
Epinephelus malabaricus
Epinephelus summana
Epinephelus tauvina
Epinephelus tukula
Grammistes sexlineatus
Hyporthodus octofasciatus
Plectropomus areolatus
Plectropomus marisrubri
Plectropomus pessuliferus
Pseudanthias squamipinnis

	<i>Pseudanthias taeniatus</i>
	<i>Variola louti</i>
Siganidae	<i>Siganus argenteus</i>
	<i>Siganus luridus</i>
	<i>Siganus rivulatus</i>
	<i>Siganus stellatus</i>
Soleidae	<i>Pardachirus marmoratus</i>
Sparidae	<i>Acanthopagrus bifasciatus</i>
	<i>Argyrops spinifer</i>
	<i>Crenidens crenidens</i>
	<i>Diplodus noct</i>
	<i>Rhabdosargus berda</i>
	<i>Rhabdosargus sarba</i>
Sphyraenidae	<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i>
	<i>Sphyraena flavicauda</i>
	<i>Sphyraena putnamae</i>
	<i>Sphyraena qenie</i>
Spratelloididae	<i>Spratelloides gracilis</i>
Stegostomatidae	<i>Stegostoma fasciatum</i>
Synanceiidae	<i>Synanceia verrucosa</i>
Syngnathidae	<i>Corythoichthys flavofasciatus</i>
	<i>Corythoichthys schultzi</i>
	<i>Dunckerocampus multiannulatus</i>
	<i>Trachyrhamphus bicoarctatus</i>
Synodontidae	<i>Saurida gracilis</i>
	<i>Synodus dermatogenys</i>
	<i>Synodus variegatus</i>
Tetradontidae	<i>Arothron diadematus</i>
	<i>Arothron hispidus</i>
	<i>Arothron immaculatus</i>
	<i>Arothron stellatus</i>
	<i>Canthigaster coronata</i>
	<i>Canthigaster cyanospilota</i>
	<i>Canthigaster margaritata</i>
	<i>Canthigaster pygmaea</i>
	<i>Lagocephalus suezensis</i>
Torpedinidae	<i>Torpedo sinuspersici</i>
Tripterygiidae	<i>Enneapterygius altipinnis</i>
	<i>Enneapterygius obscurus</i>
	<i>Enneapterygius pallidus</i>

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Vascular Plants

Table B14. Native vascular plant species confirmed in NEOM as of December 2024.

Species	Family	Comment
<i>Abutilon fruticosum</i>	Malvaceae	
<i>Achillea fragrantissima</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Achnatherum parviflorum</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Adiantum capillus-veneris</i>	Pteridaceae	
<i>Adonis dentata</i>	Ranunculaceae	
<i>Aeluropus lagopoides</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Aerva javanica</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Agathophora alopecuroides</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Aizoon canariense</i>	Aizoaceae	
<i>Ajuga chamaepitys</i> ssp. <i>tridactylites</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Alcea striata</i>	Malvaceae	
<i>Alhagi graecorum</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Alkanna orientalis</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Allium artemisietorum</i>	Amaryllidaceae	If confirmed new to KSA
<i>Allium asirense</i>	Amaryllidaceae	
<i>Allium dictyoprasum</i>	Amaryllidaceae	
<i>Allium sinaiticum</i>	Amaryllidaceae	
<i>Allium sindjarens</i>	Amaryllidaceae	
<i>Allium stamineum</i>	Amaryllidaceae	
<i>Alyssum szovitsianum</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Amaranthus graecizans</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Anabasis articulata</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Anabasis setifera</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Anarrhinum forskaohlii</i> ssp. <i>forskaohlii</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Anastatica hierochuntica</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Anchusa aegyptiaca</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Anchusa milleri</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Andrachne aspera</i>	Phyllanthaceae	
<i>Andropogon distachyos</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Androsace maxima</i>	Primulaceae	
<i>Anisosciadium isosciadium</i>	Apiaceae	
<i>Anisosciadium lanatum</i>	Apiaceae	
<i>Anthemis cotula</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Anthemis melampodina</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Anticharis glandulosa</i>	Scrophulariaceae	
<i>Anvillea garcinii</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Arabis nova</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Arenaria deflexa</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Argyrolobium crotalarioides</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Aristida adscensionis</i>	Poaceae	

<i>Arnebia decumbens</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Arnebia hispidissima</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Arnebia tinctoria</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Artemisia judaica</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Artemisia monosperma</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Artemisia sieberi</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Asparagus horridus</i>	Asparagaceae	
<i>Asphodelus fistulosus</i>	Asphodelaceae	
<i>Asphodelus refractus</i>	Asphodelaceae	
<i>Asphodelus tenuifolius</i>	Asphodelaceae	
<i>Asteriscus graveolens</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Astragalus annularis</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Astragalus arpilobus</i> ssp. <i>hauarensis</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Astragalus atropilosulus</i> ssp. <i>abyssinicus</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Astragalus bombycinus</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Astragalus caprinus</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Astragalus collenetteae</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Astragalus dactylocarpus</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Astragalus echinus</i> ssp. <i>echinus</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Astragalus eremophilus</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Astragalus schimperi</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Astragalus sieberi</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Astragalus sparsus</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Astragalus spinosus</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Astragalus tribuloides</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Astragalus vogelii</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Atractylis cancellata</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Atractylis carduus</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Atraphaxis spinosa</i>	Polygonaceae	
<i>Atriplex farinosa</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Atriplex turcomanica</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Avena barbata</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Avena clauda</i>	Poaceae	If confirmed new to KSA
<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i>	Zygophyllaceae	
<i>Ballota saxatilis</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Bassia eriophora</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Bassia muricata</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Bellevalia flexuosa</i>	Asparagaceae	
<i>Bellevalia mosheovii</i>	Asparagaceae	If confirmed new to KSA
<i>Biscutella didyma</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Bituminaria bituminosa</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Bituminaria flacida</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Blepharis ciliaris</i>	Acanthaceae	
<i>Blumea bovei</i>	Asteraceae	

<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>	Nyctaginaceae	
<i>Bolanthus filicaulis</i>	Caryophyllaceae	If confirmed new to KSA
<i>Brachypodium distachyon</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Bromus danthoniae</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Bromus fasciculatus</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Bromus pumilio</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Bromus tectorum</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Bryonia cf. cretica</i>	Cucurbitaceae	If confirmed new to KSA
<i>Buglossoides tenuiflora</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Cadaba farinosa</i>	Capparaceae	
<i>Cakile arabica</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Calendula arvensis</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Calendula tripterocarpa</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Calligonum comosum</i>	Polygonaceae	
<i>Callipeltis cucullaris</i>	Rubiaceae	
<i>Calotropis procera</i>	Apocynaceae	
<i>Campanula dulcis</i>	Campanulaceae	
<i>Campanula erinus</i>	Campanulaceae	
<i>Capparis cartilaginea</i>	Capparaceae	
<i>Capparis decidua</i>	Capparaceae	
<i>Capparis spinosa</i>	Capparaceae	
<i>Capparis spinosa</i> var. <i>mucronifolia</i>	Capparaceae	
<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Caralluma plicatiloba</i>	Apocynaceae	
<i>Carduus getulus</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Carduus pycnocephalus</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Carex distans</i>	Cyperaceae	
<i>Caroxylon cyclophyllum</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Caroxylon imbricatum</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Caroxylon spinescens</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Caroxylon vermiculatum</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Caroxylon villosum</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Carrichtera annua</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Carthamus nitidus</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Caudanthera sinaica</i>	Apocynaceae	
<i>Caylusea hexagyna</i>	Resedaceae	
<i>Cebatha pendula</i>	Menispermaceae	
<i>Cenchrus ciliaris</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Cenchrus divisus</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Cenchrus orientalis</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Cenchrus setaceus</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Centaurea eryngioides</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Centaurea scoparia</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Centaurea sinaica</i>	Asteraceae	

<i>Centaurium pulchellum</i>	Gentianaceae	
<i>Centropodia forskalii</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Cerastium dichotomum</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Chenopodiastrum murale</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Chenopodium album</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Chiliadenus montanus</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Chrozophora oblongifolia</i>	Euphorbiaceae	
<i>Chrozophora tinctoria</i>	Euphorbiaceae	
<i>Cicer judaicum</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Cistanche tubulosa</i>	Orobanchaceae	
<i>Cistanche violacea</i>	Orobanchaceae	
<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i>	Cucurbitaceae	
<i>Cleome amblyocarpa</i>	Cleomaceae	
<i>Cleome arabica</i>	Cleomaceae	
<i>Cleome chrysantha</i>	Cleomaceae	
<i>Cleome droserifolia</i>	Cleomaceae	
<i>Coincya tournefortii</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Colchicum guessfeldtianum</i>	Colchicaceae	
<i>Colchicum palaestinum</i>	Colchicaceae	
<i>Colchicum ritchii</i>	Colchicaceae	
<i>Colutea istria</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Cometes surattensis</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Commicarpus helenae</i>	Nyctaginaceae	
<i>Convolvulus cephalophorus</i>	Convolvulaceae	
<i>Convolvulus hystrix</i>	Convolvulaceae	
<i>Convolvulus oxyphyllus</i>	Convolvulaceae	
<i>Convolvulus pilosellifolius</i>	Convolvulaceae	
<i>Corbichonia decumbens</i>	Lophiocarpaceae	
<i>Cornulaca ehrenbergii</i>	Amaranthaceae	Confirmed new to KSA
<i>Cornulaca setifera</i>	Amaranthaceae	Confirmed new to KSA
<i>Cosentinia vellea</i>	Pteridaceae	
<i>Cotoneaster nummularius</i>	Rosaceae	
<i>Crambe hispanica</i>	Brassicaceae	Confirmed new to KSA
<i>Cressa cretica</i>	Convolvulaceae	
<i>Crotalaria aegyptiaca</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Crucianella ciliata</i>	Rubiaceae	
<i>Crucianella membranacea</i>	Rubiaceae	
<i>Cucumis prophetarum</i>	Cucurbitaceae	
<i>Cuprella homalocarpa</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Cuscuta planiflora</i>	Convolvulaceae	
<i>Cutandia memphitica</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Cymbopogon commutatus</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Cymbopogon schoenanthus</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Cymodocea rotundata</i>	Cymodoceaceae	

<i>Cynanchum boveanum</i>	Apocynaceae	
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Cynoglossum</i> sp. (<i>montanum</i> ?)	Boraginaceae	
<i>Cyperus conglomeratus</i>	Cyperaceae	
<i>Daphne mucronata</i> ssp. <i>linearifolia</i>	Thymelaeaceae	
<i>Delphinium sheilae</i>	Ranunculaceae	
<i>Deverra tortuosa</i>	Apiaceae	
<i>Deverra triradiata</i>	Apiaceae	
<i>Dianthus sinaicus</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Dianthus strictus</i> ssp. <i>sublaevis</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Dichanthium foveolatum</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Dipcadi erythraeum</i>	Asparagaceae	
<i>Diplotaxis acris</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Diplotaxis harra</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Diplotaxis tenuifolia</i>	Brassicaceae	Confirmed new to KSA
<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i>	Sapindaceae	
<i>Drimia maritima</i>	Asparagaceae	
<i>Ducrosia anethifolia</i>	Apiaceae	
<i>Ducrosia flabellifolia</i>	Apiaceae	
<i>Echinops erinaceus</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Echinops glaberrimus</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Echinops mandavillei</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Echium rauwolfii</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Ephedra aphylla</i>	Ephedraceae	
<i>Ephedra ciliata</i>	Ephedraceae	
<i>Ephedra pachyclada</i> ssp. <i>sinaica</i>	Ephedraceae	
<i>Eragrostis barrelieri</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Eremobium aegyptiacum</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Eremogone picta</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Erodium ciconium</i>	Geraniaceae	
<i>Erodium cicutarium</i>	Geraniaceae	
<i>Erodium crassifolium</i>	Geraniaceae	
<i>Erodium glaucophyllum</i>	Geraniaceae	
<i>Erodium laciniatum</i>	Geraniaceae	
<i>Erodium malacoides</i>	Geraniaceae	
<i>Erodium neuradifolium</i>	Geraniaceae	
<i>Erodium oxyrhinchum</i>	Geraniaceae	
<i>Erodium touchyanum</i>	Geraniaceae	
<i>Erucaria crassifolia</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Erucaria hispanica</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Eryngium glomeratum</i>	Apiaceae	
<i>Erysimum repandum</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Eschenbachia stricta</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Euphorbia chamaepeplus</i>	Euphorbiaceae	

<i>Euphorbia granulata</i>	Euphorbiaceae	
<i>Euphorbia retusa</i>	Euphorbiaceae	
<i>Euphorbia terracina</i>	Euphorbiaceae	
<i>Euryops jaberiana</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Evotrochis cf. involucrata</i>	Primulaceae	Confirming if new to KSA
<i>Farsetia aegyptia</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Farsetia burtoniae</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Farsetia longisiliqua</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Farsetia stylosa</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Ferula communis</i>	Apiaceae	
<i>Ferula sinaica</i>	Apiaceae	
<i>Ficus palmata</i>	Moraceae	
<i>Ficus palmata</i> ssp. <i>virgata</i>	Moraceae	
<i>Ficus salicifolia</i>	Moraceae	
<i>Filago desertorum</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Filago griffithii</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Forsskaolea tenacissima</i>	Urticaceae	
<i>Fumaria parviflora</i>	Papaveraceae	
<i>Gagea commutata</i>	Liliaceae	
<i>Gagea reticulata</i>	Liliaceae	
<i>Galium aparine</i>	Rubiaceae	
<i>Galium canum</i>	Rubiaceae	
<i>Galium sinaicum</i>	Rubiaceae	
<i>Galium spurium</i>	Rubiaceae	
<i>Gastrocotyle hispida</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Geranium molle</i>	Geraniaceae	
<i>Glaucium arabicum</i>	Papaveraceae	
<i>Globularia arabica</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Gomphocarpus sinaicus</i>	Apocynaceae	
<i>Gymnarrhena micrantha</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Gymnocarpos decander</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Gymnocarpos sclerocephalus</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Gypsophila capillaris</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Gypsophila pilosa</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Gypsophila viscosa</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Halocnemum strobilaceum</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Halodule pinifolia</i>	Cymodoceaceae	
<i>Halodule uninervis</i>	Cymodoceaceae	
<i>Halopeplis perfoliata</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Halophila decipiens</i>	Hydrocharitaceae	
<i>Halophila minor</i>	Hydrocharitaceae	
<i>Halophila ovalis</i>	Hydrocharitaceae	
<i>Halophila stipulacea</i>	Hydrocharitaceae	
<i>Haloxylon persicum</i>	Amaranthaceae	

<i>Haloxylon salicornicum</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Haplophyllum tuberculatum</i>	Rutaceae	
<i>Helianthemum kahiricum</i>	Cistaceae	
<i>Helianthemum ledifolium</i>	Cistaceae	
<i>Helianthemum lippii</i>	Cistaceae	
<i>Helianthemum sancti-antoni</i>	Cistaceae	
<i>Heliotropium arbainense</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Heliotropium bacciferum</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Heliotropium digynum</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Heliotropium ramosissimum</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Hemionitis acrostica</i>	Pteridaceae	
<i>Hemionitis pteridioides</i>	Pteridaceae	
<i>Herniaria hirsuta</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Hibiscus micranthus</i>	Malvaceae	
<i>Hippocrepis areolata</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Hippocrepis constricta</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Holosteum umbellatum</i> ssp. <i>glutinosum</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Hordeum murinum</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Hordeum murinum</i> ssp. <i>glaucum</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Hyoscyamus aureus</i>	Solanaceae	
<i>Hyoscyamus boveanus</i>	Solanaceae	Confirmed new to KSA
<i>Hyoscyamus desertorum</i>	Solanaceae	
<i>Hyoscyamus muticus</i>	Solanaceae	
<i>Hyoscyamus pusillus</i>	Solanaceae	
<i>Hyoscyamus</i> sp. <i>nov.</i>	Solanaceae	
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Hypecoum littorale</i>	Papaveraceae	
<i>Hypecoum pendulum</i>	Papaveraceae	
<i>Hypericum sinaicum</i>	Hypericaceae	
<i>Hyphaene thebaica</i>	Arecaceae	
<i>Ifloga spicata</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Ifloga spicata</i> ssp. <i>albescens</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Indigofera articulata</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Indigofera schimperi</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Iphiona mucronata</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Iphiona scabra</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Ipomoea pes-caprae</i>	Convolvulaceae	
<i>Isatis lusitanica</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Juncus bufonius</i>	Juncaceae	
<i>Juncus rigidus</i>	Juncaceae	
<i>Juniperus turbinata</i>	Cupressaceae	
<i>Kickxia aegyptiaca</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Kickxia collenetteana</i>	Plantaginaceae	

<i>Kickxia floribunda</i>	Plantaginaceae
<i>Kickxia pseudoscoparia</i>	Plantaginaceae
<i>Koelpinia linearis</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Kohautia caespitosa</i>	Rubiaceae
<i>Lactuca orientalis</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Lamium amplexicaule</i>	Lamiaceae
<i>Lappula spinocarpos</i>	Boraginaceae
<i>Lasiopogon muscoides</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Lasiospermum brachyglossum</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Lasiurus scindicus</i>	Poaceae
<i>Launaea capitata</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Launaea mucronata</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Launaea nudicaulis</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Launaea procumbens</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Launaea spinosa</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Lavandula coronopifolia</i>	Lamiaceae
<i>Lavandula pubescens</i>	Lamiaceae
<i>Leobordea platycarpa</i>	Fabaceae
<i>Leontice leontopetalum</i>	Berberidaceae
<i>Lepidium aucheri</i>	Brassicaceae
<i>Lepidium draba</i>	Brassicaceae
<i>Leptadenia pyrotechnica</i>	Apocynaceae
<i>Leysera leyseroides</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Limeum arabicum</i>	Limeaceae
<i>Limeum obovatum</i>	Limeaceae
<i>Limonium axillare</i>	Plumbaginaceae
<i>Linaria haelava</i>	Plantaginaceae
<i>Linaria simplex</i>	Plantaginaceae
<i>Lindenbergia indica</i>	Orobanchaceae
<i>Loeflingia hispanica</i>	Caryophyllaceae
<i>Lolium rigidum</i>	Poaceae
<i>Lomelosia olivieri</i>	Caprifoliaceae
<i>Lomelosia porphyroneura</i>	Caprifoliaceae
<i>Lotus glinoides</i>	Fabaceae
<i>Lotus halophilus</i>	Fabaceae
<i>Lycium shawii</i>	Solanaceae
<i>Lysimachia arvensis</i>	Primulaceae
<i>Maerua crassifolia</i>	Capparaceae
<i>Malva ludwigii</i>	Malvaceae
<i>Malva parviflora</i>	Malvaceae
<i>Malva verticillata</i>	Malvaceae
<i>Matthiola arabica</i>	Brassicaceae
<i>Matthiola longipetala</i>	Brassicaceae
<i>Maytenus linearifolius</i>	Celastraceae

<i>Medicago laciniata</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Melica persica</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Melilotus indicus</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Mentha longifolia</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Mercurialis annua</i>	Euphorbiaceae	
<i>Mesembryanthemum cryptanthum</i>	Aizoaceae	
<i>Micromeria imbricata</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Micromeria microphylla</i>	Lamiaceae	If confirmed new to KSA
<i>Microparacaryum intermedium</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Misopates orontium</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Moltkiopsis ciliata</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Monsonia heliotropioides</i>	Geraniaceae	
<i>Monsonia nivea</i>	Geraniaceae	
<i>Moraea sisyrinchium</i>	Iridaceae	
<i>Morettia canescens</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Morettia parviflora</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Moringa peregrina</i>	Moringaceae	
<i>Muscari longipes</i> ssp. <i>longipes</i>	Asparagaceae	Confirmed new to KSA
<i>Muscari tenuiflorum</i>	Asparagaceae	
<i>Myagrum perfoliatum</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Myosotis ramosissima</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Myrtus communis</i>	Myrtaceae	
<i>Nanorrhinum acerbianum</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Nanorrhinum hastatum</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Nanorrhinum scoparium</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Nepeta glomerata</i>	Lamiaceae	If confirmed new to KSA
<i>Nepeta sheilae</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Neurada procumbens</i>	Neuradaceae	
<i>Nitraria retusa</i>	Nitrariaceae	
<i>Noaea mucronata</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Nonea echioides</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Notoceras bicornis</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Oceana serrulata</i>	Cymodoceaceae	
<i>Ochradenus baccatus</i>	Resedaceae	
<i>Odontarrhena subspinosa</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Ogastemma pusillum</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Oligomeris linifolia</i>	Resedaceae	
<i>Oloptum miliaceum</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Onobrychis ptolemaica</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Ononis natrix</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Ononis sicula</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Onopordum ambiguum</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Origanum syriacum</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Orobanche aegyptiaca</i>	Orobanchaceae	

<i>Orobanche cernua</i>	Orobanchaceae	
<i>Osteospermum vaillantii</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Otoglyphis factorovskyi</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Otostegia fruticosa</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Otostegia fruticosa</i> ssp. <i>schimperii</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Ouret lanata</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Pallenis hierichuntica</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Pancratium sickenbergeri</i>	Amaryllidaceae	
<i>Panicum turgidum</i>	Amaryllidaceae	
<i>Papaver decaisnei</i>	Papaveraceae	
<i>Papaver glaucum</i>	Papaveraceae	
<i>Paracaryum rugulosum</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Parietaria alsinefolia</i>	Urticaceae	
<i>Paronychia arabica</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Paronychia sinaica</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Peganum harmala</i>	Nitrariaceae	
<i>Pergularia tomentosa</i>	Apocynaceae	
<i>Periploca aphylla</i>	Apocynaceae	
<i>Phagnalon barbeyanum</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Phagnalon nitidum</i>	Asteraceae	Confirmed new to KSA
<i>Phagnalon schweinfurthii</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Phagnalon sinaicum</i> (sp. nov. aff.?)	Asteraceae	
<i>Phalaris minor</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Phlomis brachyodon</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>	Arecaceae	
<i>Phragmites australis</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Picris babylonica</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Picris cyanocarpa</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Pimpinella cretica</i>	Apiaceae	
<i>Piptatherum holciforme</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Pistacia khinjuk</i>	Anacardiaceae	
<i>Plantago afra</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Plantago albicans</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Plantago amplexicaulis</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Plantago ciliata</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Plantago coronopus</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Plantago cylindrica</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Plantago maris-mortui</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Plantago ovata</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Plantago psammophila</i>	Plantaginaceae	
<i>Plantago sinaica</i>	Plantaginaceae	Confirmed new to KSA
<i>Plicosepalus acaciae</i>	Loranthaceae	
<i>Plocama calycoptera</i>	Rubiaceae	
<i>Poa sinaica</i>	Poaceae	

<i>Podonosma orientalis</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Polycarpaea repens</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Polycarpaea robbairea</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Polygala sinaica</i> var. <i>glabrescens</i>	Polygalaceae	
<i>Polypogon monspeliensis</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Prunus korshinskyi</i>	Rosaceae	
<i>Pseudodictamnus undulatus</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Pseudolappula sinaica</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Pteranthus dichotomus</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Pterocephalus brevis</i>	Caprifoliaceae	
<i>Pterocephalus sanctus</i>	Caprifoliaceae	
<i>Pulicaria arabica</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Pulicaria guestii</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Pulicaria incisa</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Pulicaria undulata</i> ssp. <i>undulata</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Pycnocycla saxatilis</i>	Apiaceae	
<i>Pycnocycla tomentosa</i>	Apiaceae	
<i>Ramaliella intricata</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Ramaliella musilii</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Ramaliella tortuosissima</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Reaumuria hirtella</i>	Tamaricaceae	
<i>Reichardia tingitana</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Reseda arabica</i>	Resedaceae	
<i>Reseda muricata</i>	Resedaceae	
<i>Reseda pentagyna</i>	Resedaceae	
<i>Retama raetam</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Rhamnus disperma</i>	Rhamnaceae	
<i>Rhamphospermum arvense</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Rhanterium epapposum</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Rhazya stricta</i>	Apocynaceae	
<i>Rhynchosia minima</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Roemeria hybrida</i>	Papaveraceae	If confirmed new to KSA
<i>Rosa</i> cf. <i>arabica</i>	Rosaceae	If confirmed new to KSA
<i>Rosa pulverulenta</i>	Rosaceae	
<i>Rumex spinosus</i>	Polygonaceae	
<i>Rumex vesicarius</i>	Polygonaceae	
<i>Sageretia thea</i>	Rhamnaceae	
<i>Salix acmophylla</i>	Salicaceae	
<i>Salvadora persica</i>	Salvadoraceae	
<i>Salvia aegyptiaca</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Salvia deserti</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Salvia spinosa</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Samolus valerandi</i>	Primulaceae	
<i>Savignya parviflora</i>	Brassicaceae	

<i>Scandix stellata</i>	Apiaceae	
<i>Schimpera arabica</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Schismus arabicus</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Schismus barbatus</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Schoenus nigricans</i>	Cyperaceae	
<i>Scirpoides holoschoenus</i>	Cyperaceae	
<i>Scorzonera schweinfurthii</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Scrophularia deserti</i>	Scrophulariaceae	
<i>Scrophularia hypericifolia</i>	Scrophulariaceae	
<i>Scrophularia libanotica</i>	Scrophulariaceae	
<i>Scrophularia peyronii</i>	Scrophulariaceae	
<i>Scrophularia xylorrhiza</i>	Scrophulariaceae	
<i>Searsia tripartita</i>	Anacardiaceae	
<i>Seetzenia orientalis</i>	Zygophyllaceae	
<i>Senecio flavus</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Senecio glaucus</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Senecio hoggariensis</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Senna italica</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Sideritis montana</i>	Lamiaceae	If confirmed new to KSA
<i>Silene arabica</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Silene burchellii</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Silene corylina</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Silene hussonii</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Silene linearis</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Silene sp. aff. peduncularis</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Silene schimperiana</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Silene villosa</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Sisymbrium erysimoides</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Sisymbrium irio</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Sisymbrium septulatum</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Soda rosmarinus</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Soda schweinfurthii</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Solanum villosum</i>	Solanaceae	
<i>Solenostemma arghel</i>	Apocynaceae	
<i>Spergularia diandra</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Spergularia flaccida</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Spergularia marina</i>	Caryophyllaceae	
<i>Stachys aegyptiaca</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Sternbergia clusiana</i>	Amaryllidaceae	If confirmed new to KSA
<i>Stipa hohenackeriana</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Stipagrostis ciliata</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Stipagrostis drarii</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Stipagrostis hirtigluma</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Stipagrostis obtusa</i>	Poaceae	

<i>Stipagrostis plumosa</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Stipagrostis raddiana</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Stipellula capensis</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Strigosella africana</i>	Brassicaceae	
<i>Suaeda fruticosa</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Suaeda monoica</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Suaeda vermiculata</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Syringodium isoetifolium</i>	Cymodoceaceae	
<i>Tamarix aphylla</i>	Tamaricaceae	
<i>Tamarix nilotica</i>	Tamaricaceae	
<i>Tanacetum sinaicum</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Tephrosia nubica</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> ssp. <i>apollinea</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Tetrapogon villosus</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Teucrium leucocladum</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Teucrium oliverianum</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Teucrium polium</i>	Lamiaceae	If confirmed new to KSA
<i>Thalassia hemprichii</i>	Hydrocharitaceae	
<i>Thalassodendron ciliatum</i>	Cymodoceaceae	
<i>Thymbra nabateorum</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Thymbra thymbrifolia</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Thymus decussatus</i>	Lamiaceae	
<i>Traganum nudatum</i>	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Tribulus pentandrus</i>	Zygophyllaceae	
<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	Zygophyllaceae	
<i>Trichodesma africanum</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Trichodesma ehrenbergii</i>	Boraginaceae	
<i>Tricholaena teneriffae</i>	Poaceae	
<i>Trigonella stellata</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Trigonella cylindrica</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Tripleurospermum auriculatum</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Tulipa biflora</i>	Liliaceae	
<i>Typha domingensis</i>	Typhaceae	
<i>Urospermum picroides</i>	Asteraceae	
<i>Vachellia flava</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Vachellia gerrardi</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Vachellia tortilis</i> ssp. <i>raddiana</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Vachellia tortilis</i> ssp. <i>tortilis</i>	Fabaceae	
<i>Valeriana szovitsiana</i>	Caprifoliaceae	
<i>Verbascum decaisneanum</i>	Scrophulariaceae	
<i>Verbascum deserticola</i>	Scrophulariaceae	
<i>Verbascum longibracteatum</i>	Scrophulariaceae	
<i>Verbascum schimperianum</i>	Scrophulariaceae	

<i>Verbascum shiqricum</i>	Scrophulariaceae
<i>Verbascum sinaiticum</i>	Scrophulariaceae
<i>Veronica anagallis-aquatica</i>	Plantaginaceae
<i>Veronica rubrifolia</i>	Plantaginaceae
<i>Withania somnifera</i>	Solanaceae
<i>Zilla spinosa</i>	Brassicaceae
<i>Ziziphus spina-christi</i>	Rhamnaceae
<i>Zoegea purpurea</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Zosima absinthiifolia</i>	Apiaceae
<i>Zygophyllum album</i>	Zygophyllaceae
<i>Zygophyllum arabicum</i>	Zygophyllaceae
<i>Zygophyllum bruguieri</i>	Zygophyllaceae
<i>Zygophyllum coccineum</i>	Zygophyllaceae
<i>Zygophyllum decumbens</i>	Zygophyllaceae
<i>Zygophyllum glutinosum</i>	Zygophyllaceae
<i>Zygophyllum hamiense</i>	Zygophyllaceae
<i>Zygophyllum indicum</i>	Zygophyllaceae
<i>Zygophyllum molle</i>	Zygophyllaceae
<i>Zygophyllum orientale</i>	Zygophyllaceae
<i>Zygophyllum paulayanum</i>	Zygophyllaceae

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Table B15. Native plant species that possibly occur in NEOM.

Species	Family
<i>Anabasis lachnantha</i>	Amaranthaceae
<i>Apteranthes europaea</i>	Apocynaceae
<i>Apteranthes tuberculata</i>	Apocynaceae
<i>Arthrocaulon macrostachyum</i>	Amaranthaceae
<i>Astragalus asterias</i>	Fabaceae
<i>Astragalus crenatus</i>	Fabaceae
<i>Astragalus palaestinus</i>	Fabaceae
<i>Astragalus tenuifolius</i>	Fabaceae
<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>	Plantaginaceae
<i>Ballota adenophora</i>	Lamiaceae
<i>Boerhavia coccinea</i>	Nyctaginaceae
<i>Bolanthus hirsutus</i>	Caryophyllaceae
<i>Bromus moeszii</i>	Poaceae
<i>Bromus rigidus</i>	Poaceae
<i>Caroxylon jordanicola</i>	Amaranthaceae
<i>Caroxylon tetrandrum</i>	Amaranthaceae
<i>Centaurea ammocyanus</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Centaurea damascena</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Centaurea palleescens</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Centaurea pulchella</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Chaenorhinum rubrifolium</i>	Plantaginaceae

<i>Chiladenus iphionoides</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Chorispora purpurascens</i>	Brassicaceae
<i>Cleome quinquenervia</i>	Cleomaceae
<i>Cleome rupicola</i>	Cleomaceae
<i>Clypeola jonthlaspi</i>	Brassicaceae
<i>Colchicum schimperii</i>	Colchicaceae
<i>Colchicum triphyllum</i>	Colchicaceae
<i>Colchicum tunicatum</i>	Colchicaceae
<i>Commicarpus sinuatus</i>	Nyctaginaceae
<i>Convolvulus cephalopodus</i> ssp. <i>bushiricus</i>	Convolvulaceae
<i>Convolvulus glomeratus</i>	Convolvulaceae
<i>Convolvulus prostratus</i>	Convolvulaceae
<i>Convolvulus spicatus</i>	Convolvulaceae
<i>Cornulaca monacantha</i>	Amaranthaceae
<i>Cotula anthemoides</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Crocus haussknechtii</i>	Iridaceae
<i>Crocus naqabensis</i>	Iridaceae
<i>Dipcadi serotinum</i>	Asparagaceae
<i>Dracocephalum royleanum</i>	Lamiaceae
<i>Galium khahelianum</i>	Rubiaceae
<i>Herniaria hemistemon</i>	Caryophyllaceae
<i>Hordeum secalinum</i>	Poaceae
<i>Hypertelis cerviana</i>	Molluginaceae
<i>Iris florentina</i>	Iridaceae
<i>Lavandula citriodora</i>	Lamiaceae
<i>Leucas inflata</i>	Lamiaceae
<i>Limonium pruinosum</i>	Plumbaginaceae
<i>Lindenbergia sinaica</i>	Orobanchaceae
<i>Lycium depressum</i>	Solanaceae
<i>Malva aegyptia</i>	Malvaceae
<i>Malva neglecta</i>	Malvaceae
<i>Mesembryanthemum nodiflorum</i>	Aizoaceae
<i>Micromeria danaensis</i>	Lamiaceae
<i>Muscari bicolor</i>	Asparagaceae
<i>Nepeta cilicica</i>	Lamiaceae
<i>Paronychia argentea</i>	Caryophyllaceae
<i>Picris rhagadioloides</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Prunus arabica</i>	Roseaceae
<i>Ranunculus rionii</i>	Ranunculaceae
<i>Reseda alba</i>	Resedaceae
<i>Reseda decursiva</i>	Resedaceae
<i>Reseda stenostachya</i>	Resedaceae
<i>Rheum palaestinum</i>	Polygonaceae
<i>Romulea petraea</i>	Iridaceae

<i>Rosa abyssinica</i>	Rosaceae
<i>Rosa pulverulenta</i>	Rosaceae
<i>Rumex cyprius</i>	Polygonaceae
<i>Salix mucronata</i>	Lamiaceae
<i>Salvia schimperi</i>	Lamiaceae
<i>Scandix pecten-veneris</i>	Apiaceae
<i>Scorzoneroideis laciniata</i>	Asteraceae
<i>Scrophularia xanthoglossa</i>	Scrophulariaceae
<i>Senna alexandrina</i> var. <i>alexandrina</i>	Fabaceae
<i>Silene arabica</i>	Carophyllaceae
<i>Silene burchellii</i>	Caryophyllaceae
<i>Silene colorata</i>	Caryophyllaceae
<i>Silene coniflora</i>	Caryophyllaceae
<i>Silene oliveriana</i>	Caryophyllaceae
<i>Silene</i> sp. aff. <i>peduncularis</i>	Caryophyllaceae
<i>Silene schimperiana</i>	Caryophyllaceae
<i>Silene villosa</i>	Caryophyllaceae
<i>Solanum incanum</i>	Solanaceae
<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	Solanaceae
<i>Stachys schimperi</i>	Lamiaceae
<i>Stipa lagascae</i>	Poaceae
<i>Tamarix aphylla</i>	Tamaricaceae
<i>Tamarix aucheriana</i>	Tamaricaceae
<i>Tamarix tetragyna</i>	Tamaricaceae
<i>Tephrosia uniflora</i>	Fabaceae
<i>Tephrosia uniflora</i> ssp. <i>uniflora</i>	Fabaceae
<i>Tribulus bimucronatus</i>	Zygophyllaceae
<i>Tribulus macropterus</i>	Zygophyllaceae
<i>Trigonella glabra</i> ssp. <i>glabra</i>	Fabaceae
<i>Umbilicus luteus</i>	Crassulaceae
<i>Valeriana oxyrhyncha</i>	Caprifoliaceae
<i>Veronica anagalloides</i>	Plantaginaceae
<i>Veronica beccabunga</i>	Plantaginaceae
<i>Zaleya pentandra</i>	Aizoaceae
<i>Zuvanda crenulate</i>	Brassicaceae

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